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Description of the activities: Organizing and hosting workshop on the outcome of the activities within WP4 on corrosion in HLM.				
SIGNATURES				
Author: S.Gavrilov		WP Leader: G. Ferro		Coordinator: P. Agostini

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List of participants

Name	Institution
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Aktaa Jarir	KIT IAM

Questions

The questions in the list below were raised during the workshop and specified for the discussion session. Unfortunately, due to lack of time the discussion was very limited and the only written comments provided after the workshop

1. Characterization of corrosion: what is the best way?

Comment by Serguei Gavrilov: The developed at KIT methodology for regular measurements every 15° of the circumference together with applied at SCK CEN practices to measure the depth of damages above certain threshold(e.g. 5µm) on few cross sections of the sample might be sufficient to characterize developed dissolution corrosion. In case of localized corrosion as for instance observed on austenitic steels in flowing oxygen containing LBE at low temperature range number of the cross sections should be increased and they should be done at the spots observed by surface examination techniques. To characterize and measure efficiency of the corrosion mitigation surface treatment one should develop dedicated techniques. Those techniques also depends on the qualification approach are selected for.

2. What can we conclude for the difference in corrosion of base material and welded joints?

Comment by Serguei Gavrilov: Development of the dissolution corrosion

3. Difference between LMC in LBE and lead: what is the difference and why? If Cr solubility difference in LBE and Pb can be the explanation?

Comment by Lukáš Košek: Bare steels in Pb: Surface finish and presence of cold worked hardened layer controls presence of localized corrosion attack – oxidation or Pb penetration. Exact conditions are unclear and require more work. In Pb and oxygen seems to be positive. In LBE we have seen opposite. Long term effect is also impossible to predict.

Comment by Serguei Gavrilov: It seems indeed that for sufficiently oxygen containing Pb the chance to form protective oxide layer on austenitic steels is higher in comparison with LBE. However, the depth of the dissolution corrosion in low oxygen liquid metal is comparable between liquid lead and LBE.

4. Corrosion mitigation. What are the lessons learned from application of different surface treatments?

Comment by Lukáš Košek: Coatings in Pb: Al₂O₃ coating is thermodynamically stable in Pb, but detonation gun application doesn't look feasible – too many defects leading to oxidation of substrate and penetration. FeCrAl looks like solution.

5. What is the difference in corrosion of FeCr and FeCrNi steels? Which corrodes more?

Comment by Lukáš Košek: Material loss of Grade 91 (9Cr-1Mo) steel and Eurofer 97 during first 8000hr at 480°C at 1E-7 in Pb – usually uniform oxidation without any localized issues. Comparison with 316L and 15-15Ti is complicated since localized character of corrosion in lead. General corrosion loss of austenitic steels is smaller F-M steels, but If we consider the maximum observed damage at 4000hr, than it can be worse.

Additional comment by Lukáš Košek: Maybe 1E-8 to 1E-9 wt%. O can slow down the oxidation in F-M steels enough to outperform the austenitic in general loss as well. Russian Si steel have “no corrosion issues for 50 000hr” as they showed.

Comment by Serguei Gavrilov: In oxygen containing LBE we are observing different corrosion mechanisms in 316L and in T91. For 316L it is typical formation of protective sub micrometer oxide scale with local pitting type dissolution corrosion. For T91 in the same conditions double layers oxide film of few micrometers thick is observed. Local dissolution corrosion attacks are also observed. The depth of dissolution corrosion seems to be less in T91 in the same conditions. However, there are very few cases of very deep attack in T91, which exceeds the depths of the dissolution corrosion on austenitic steels samples were observed in CORRIDA and in CRAFT loop.

6. LMC for design. Which parameters should be controlled to minimize corrosion (Jarir Aktaa)

Comment by Lukáš Košek: Follow the streamline design, in case of oxygen-controlled strategy of corrosion protection – no dead space with stagnant coolant. Oxygen level at many locations. From corrosion experiments point of view the following parameters should be controlled: Temperature / Flow velocity / Oxygen sensors (multiple) / Temperature difference / Concentration of corrosion products (how to measure?)

Comment by Serguei Gavrilov: The phenomenology of LMC is quite complex and the current understanding is not sufficient to make the complete list of recommendations for the design. The corrosion rate of 0.127 mm/year is suggested as the maximum allowable in non-mandatory recommendations of ASME code (Section III Appendix W). If corrosion rates exceeded that limit it is recommended to look for special corrosion mitigation measures rather than to increase corrosion allowance for thickness of the components. The latter is not considered as good practice for incorporation of corrosion in the design since might create additional problems as excess of corrosion products, additional thermal stresses due to increase of wall thickness, etc. For MYRRHA structural components the maximum temperature is significantly lower in comparison with the testing temperatures used in GEMMA program. The corrosion rate of 20 µm/year measure in CRAFT exposure of 20.000 hours for 316L steel is sufficiently low and do not require specific design implication for MYRRHA.

7. Temperature thresholds for LMC (Massimo Angiolini)

No comments on this question

Corrosion performance of austenitic steels at 400 °C in flowing LBE with 2×10^{-7} mass% dissolved oxygen for 20,000 h

Valentyn Tsisar, Serguei Gavrilov, Erich Stergar.

Materials, samples and surface state

Steel	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	Cu	V	W	Al	Ti	C	N	P	S	B
316L	16.73	9.97	2.05	1.81	0.67	0.23	0.07	0.02	0.018	-	0.019	0.029	0.032	0.0035	-
1.4970	15.15	15.11	1.21	1.85	0.58	0.026	0.034	0.01	0.017	0.41	0.11	0.008	0.012	<0.0005	0.0052

- HV₅₀ = 132 kgf/mm²
- Grain size averaged 45 µm (G 6)
- Annealing twins.

1.4970 rod

Remi Delville

- HV₅₀ = 188 kgf/mm²
- Very heterogeneous microstructure

Cylindrical (KIT type) samples
Ø8 x 35 mm

- Surface after turning:
 - Pattern with turning marks (1) with distance of 80 µm in-between two neighboring marks;
 - A non-regular marks (2) aligned in parallel to the main axis of sample;
 - Spot-type flaws (3).

Experiment

Test parameters

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Target parameters:

- 400 °C
- 2×10^{-7} mass % O
- 6 kg/s \sim 2 m/s

Available exposures:

- Rod samples of 316L and 1.4970:
4372 h; 5632 h; 10,004 h; 13,025 h;
16,714 h and 19,732 h.

Thermodynamic evaluation

- At 400 °C in LBE with $\sim 2 \times 10^{-7}$ mass% dissolved oxygen, the main steel constituents like Fe and Cr should oxidize while Ni, Pb and Bi cannot.
- Oxidation potential of the liquid LBE is high enough to provide in-situ formation of scale based on the Fe and Cr.

Carsten Schroer, Olaf Wedemeyer, Juergen Konyas
Nuclear Engineering and Design 241 (2011) 4913–4923

Results

~10,000 h

316L

1.4970

- Samples of 316L and 1.4970 steels are irregularly covered by the solidified LBE;
- Coverage of surface by solidified LBE might indirectly indicate about the level of dissolution attack: the larger the coverage of surface by the LBE the better wetting and the higher chance of dissolution attack.

~10,000 h

1.4970S

Samples are cleaned from LBE in $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}_2-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1-1-1) mixture at room temperature.

Corrosion response consists of:

- Oxidation
- Dissolution

Surface examinations

316L, ~10,000 h.

Surface is cleaned from LBE in $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}_2-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1-1-1) mixture at room temperature.

Groove-type corrosion damages

Localized attack develops in connection with initial surface pattern obtained after machining of samples

~4400 h

Surface examinations

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- ❑ Pit-type corrosion damage;
- ❑ Pit epicenter in the view of tetragonal pyramid – the triple junction of grain boundaries;
- ❑ Preferential corrosion along microstructural constituents - grain boundaries and deformation twins;
- ❑ Empty space was filled by LBE before cleaning.

316L, ~20,000 h

Surface is cleaned chemically from solidified LBE

316L

20,000 h

1.4970

a

c

b

d

□ Thin oxide films cover surface of samples confirming possibility of in-situ oxidation

□ Shift of binding energies to the higher values in comparison with peaks related to pure metals confirms presence of surface oxide film Fe_xCr_{3-x}O₄

316L

Corrosion intact surface

1.4970

□ Protective oxidation

Localized corrosion

□ Failure of oxide film and initiation of localized solution-based corrosion

Effect of surface turning on corrosion response

Results

Back scattered electron images of bulk and near surface zones of initial sample of 316L steel after final surface machining by turning.

- Grains in bulk are intersected by single annealing twins;
- Dimming of grains near-surface as a result of deformation;
- Near surface grains are intersected by multiple deformation bands.

Effect of surface turning on corrosion response

Electron Back Scatter Diffraction (EBSD)

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As-machined
sample

Grain Average Misorientation Map

Kernel Average Misorientation Map

Effect of surface turning on corrosion response

Electron Back Scatter Diffraction (EBSD)

23

As-machined sample

Effect of surface turning on corrosion response

316L; ~20,000 h.

- ❑ Structural-assisted corrosion in deformed zone;
- ❑ Corrosion does not exceed the thickness of near surface deformed zone.

Results

Similar conditions of LBE:

- 400 °C
- ~10⁻⁷ mass% O
- 2 m/s

Vladislav Tsinar, Serguei Gavrilov, Carsten Schroer, Erich Stergar, Corrosion Science 174 (2020) 108852.

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- The corrosion data from CRAFT and CORRIDA loops show very good conformity and are complementary to each other;
- In spite of the different operation history of the loops, the very similar results might be obtained by providing similar conditions of test with respect to temperature, flow velocity and oxygen concentration in the Pb-Bi eutectic.

Conclusions

Thank you for your attention!

Effect of deformation on development of dissolution corrosion of 316L in LBE

Experimental

Material: 316L DEMETRA

Deformation 20, 40 & 60% at RT

The gage cut in 3 samples

Surface preparation: After deformation the surface is polished with diamond suspension up to 3 μm

Exposure in low oxygen static LBE 1000, 2500 & 5000 hours

set-up placed in low oxygen glove box

Microstructure deformed samples: EBSD

20%

40%

60%

Exposure: oxygen concentration <math> < 10^{-10}</math> mass%

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Corrosion characterization

Surface examination

Regular measurements

24 measurements
(15° sectors)

Deepest corrosion measurements

Up to 100 measurements / cross section

Morphology of corrosion damages

Exposure : 1000 hours

Corrosion depth measurements presentation

The results of measurements

Accelerated penetration along twin boundaries

(K. Lambrinou et al., *JNM 490* (2017), p. 9-27)

Mechanism of corrosion development

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- **Twins are easy paths for propagation of dissolution corrosion**
- **Higher density of twins – deeper dissolution attack**

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Plastic deformation of near surface zone

Tensile samples are fabricated by turning

Near surface deformed layer up to 100 μm

Further deformation

X+0/20/40/60 %

Heterogeneous deformation

Assessment of deformation in near surface layer

Assessment of deformation in near surface layer

Time dependence

Conclusions

- The propagation of dissolution corrosion in austenitic steels is very dependent on the microstructure
- The deformation of 316L creates deformation twins, which serves as the paths for accelerated penetration of LBE
- Depth of corrosion depends linearly on the deformation percentage
- Fabrication of samples by turning introduce near surface deformation layer up to 100 μm deep
- Corrosion propagates quick in the near surface deformation layer but can be retarded in “twins free” microstructure

Research Centre

GEMMA

Generation IV Materials Maturity

scl: cen

Belgian Nuclear Research Centre

H2020 GEMMA: Workshop on HLM corrosion

316L welded joints corrosion in LBE

A. Lescur, V. Tsisar, S. Gavrilov, E. Stergar

Outline

Overview performed experiments & methods

Results

Low oxygen conditions

Controlled oxygen conditions

Preliminary conclusions

Overview performed experiments & methods

Sample extraction & preparation

Samples **stagnant** conditions

1 sample = 2 materials (BM+WM)

Samples **flowing** conditions (CRAFT)

1 sample = 1 material

Before exposure: polish up to 3 μm,
In case of 2 materials: polish up to 3 μm+ etch (Carpenter300)+ polish to 3 μm

Low oxygen conditions

Exposure conditions – low oxygen experiments

3000 h at 500 °C

3 samples in 1 stagnant pots

Low oxygen conditions – 1000 h 500 °C

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Low oxygen conditions - 3000 h 500 °C

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Low oxygen conditions

GTAW BM

SAW BM

GTAW WM

SAW WM

3000 h

Controlled oxygen conditions

Exposure conditions – controlled oxygen

4320 h at 400 °C, flowing
4 samples per cycle

[O] = 3.10^{-8} wt%

[O] = ???

4320 h @ 3.10^{-8} wt% [O] (cycle 5)

4320 h @ 2.10^{-7} wt% [O] (cycle 6)

Controlled oxygen conditions – 2000 h @ 400 °C

No corrosion found on all cross sections of all material (BM//WM) after 2000 hours

OM before cleaning

SAW BM

SEM after cleaning

GTAW BM

GTAW WM

SAW BM

SAW WM

Controlled oxygen conditions – 2000 h @ 400 °C – [O]=?

SAW BM

GTAW WM

SAW WM

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Controlled oxygen conditions – 4320 h @ 400 °C CRAFT cy5

[O] = $3 \cdot 10^{-8}$ wt%

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GTAW BM

SAW BM

GTAW WM

SAW WM

SAW WM

Controlled oxygen conditions – 4320 h @ 400 °C CRAFT cy6

[O] = 2.10⁻⁷ wt%

60

GTAW BM

SAW BM

GTAW WM

SAW WM

H2020 DEMMA Project No. 755239

Conclusions

Conclusions

Low oxygen conditions

- During low oxygen conditions, WM is more affected by dissolution based corrosion than BM
- Microstructural features play a crucial role: orientation of dendrites and inherent property of being a 3D connected network aids in increasing the corrosion rate in WM

Conclusions

Controlled oxygen conditions

- WM seems to be more robust against LBE corrosion than BM in flowing LBE environment
- Microstructure seems to play less of a role for the initiation of the LBE corrosion in flowing LBE environment
- In WM the LBE penetrates along phase boundaries between austenite and ferrite. Once penetrated along the phase boundary, the corrosion proceeds at the expense of the austenite phase
- In stagnant LBE no corrosion is observed after 2000 h at 400°C with $[O] = 3.10^{-8}$ wt%

Conclusions

General

- The presence of deformation twins (due to deformation layer) accelerates corrosion, both in terms of initiation and propagation, both in low oxygen and in controlled oxygen conditions
- WM and BM behave differently in the presence of dissolved oxygen compared to low oxygen conditions in the LBE
- Further investigation is still necessary and planned

Research Centre

Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie,
l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile

GEMMA Workshop on HLM corrosion

Corrosion of model alloys in LBE at 450/550°

Online meeting 3th November 2021

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1111 1010 0000

Introduction

- The GEMMA T4.4 we performed a study on the influence of the minor alloying elements on the oxidation process in molten lead and lead bismuth
- The initiating event in HLM corrosion is poor performance of the FeCr oxide in this environment
- The actual corrosion process in HLM, after the failure of the oxide skin, is indeed the dissolution of the steel that depending on the boundary conditions of
 - temperature,
 - temperature gradient in the system,
 - oxygen concentration
 - presence of contamination in the meltmay lead to severe damage of the structural steels.
- The final task is to contribute to a better understanding of the mechanisms by which the oxidation in heavy liquid metals is not protective
- Support the development of a model of the corrosion damage in HLM

T 4.4 workplan

Corrosion tests of FeCr and FeCrNi model alloys in Pb and PbBi varying the temperature, oxygen and time of exposure

- ✓ Samples with polished surface up to 1 μm finish

	Environment	Material	Temperature	[O] wt. %	Time of Exposure (h)
CIEMAT	LBE	FeCrNi	500°C	10-5, 10-7, 10-8	1000
CNR	LBE	FeCr,	450°C,	10-5	50, 100, 200, 500
		FeCrNi	550°C		
ENEA	LBE	FeCr,	450°C,	10-5	1000, 2500, 5000
		FeCrNi	550°C		
CVR	Pb	FeCr,	450°C,	10-5	50, 100, 200, 500,
		FeCrNi	550°C		

FeCr & FeCrNi model alloys

p.A.

id

ates

COMPOSIZIONE CHIMICA [%]															
Fe	Ni	Cu	Cr	W	Mo	Nb	Al	Ti	Si	Mn	P	C	S	O	N
<i>bal</i>			16,00												
<i>bal</i>			18,00												
<i>bal</i>	<0,05		17,00				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,05	<0,01		
<i>bal</i>	<0,05		16,90				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,01	<0,002		

min
max
aim
real

Table 1. Chemical composition of the BZ1261 cast

COMPOSIZIONE CHIMICA [%]															
Fe	Ni	Cu	Cr	W	Mo	Nb	Al	Ti	Si	Mn	P	C	S	O	N
<i>bal</i>	12,00		16,00												
<i>bal</i>	14,00		18,00												
<i>bal</i>	13,00		17,00				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,05	<0,01		
<i>bal</i>	12,80		17,10				<0,03		<0,05		<0,05	<0,01	<0,002		

min
max
aim
real

Table 2. Chemical composition of the BZ1262 cast

Experimental

HLM conditioning by bubbling Ar+H₂

One side of the samples was polished to 1 mm finish

One face of the samples was not polished

Samples were then cleaned with acetone and put in the HLM

During the tests the temperature and [O] have been maintained via a control system

For the observations in plane view, the specimens after the LBE have been immersed in a diluted solution of CH₃COOH-H₂O₂-C₂H₅OH for 24 hours under stirring to selectively remove the liquid metal

Experimental

SEM characterizations in plane view and in then longitudinal cross section

- ✓ SEM plane view and x-section:
- ✓ Thickness & Morphology of the oxide (top view, x-section)
- ✓ Max and average penetration of the lead
- ✓ Composition profiles by and EDS

- ✓ Thickness of the oxide and local PbBi penetrations have been evaluated in several equidistant areas along the cross section

• X-section samples preparation

List of the samples analysed by SEM-EDS

n.	Material	ENEACode	Exp. Time	Exp. T/°C
1	FeCrNi	24420	1000h	450
2	FeCrNi	24520	1000h	450
3	FeCrNi	24620	2500h	450
5	FeCrNi	24820	5000h	450
7	FeCrNi	04021	49h	450
8	FeCrNi	08820 (1)	1000 h	550
9	FeCrNi	08920 (1)	1000 h	550
10	FeCrNi	08620*	2500 h	550
11	FeCrNi	08720	2500 h	550
12	FeCrNi	08520	5000 h	550
13	FeCrNi	25120	64h	550
14	FeCrNi	09020	94h	550
15	FeCrNi	09220	200h	550
16	FeCrNi	03821	49h	550

n.	Material	ENEACode	Exp. Time	Exp. T/°C
1	FeCr	23620	1000h	450
2	FeCr	23920	2500h	450
3	FeCr	24020	5064h	450
4	FeCr	07420	1000h	550
6	FeCr	07520	1000h	550
7	FeCr	07620	2545h	550
8	FeCr	07720*	2545h	550
9	FeCr	07920	5014 h	550

FeCrNi 450° C LBE

FeCrNi 450° C 49h

Very thin oxide with detachments
Local dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium

FeCrNi 450° C 1000h

Very thin oxide with detachments
Extended dissolution attack with depletion of Ni and Chromium

HV | mag | det | x: -6.4582 mm | y: 18.6461 mm | WD | 50 µm | 20.00 kV | 2.098 x | BSED | 10.6 mm | 4520_FeCrNi_LBE_1000h_450C_H.C

HV | mag | det | x: -6.7678 mm | y: 18.6290 mm | WD | 20 µm | 20.00 kV | 5.000 x | BSED | 10.6 mm | 4520_FeCrNi_LBE_1000h_450C_H.C

HV | mag | det | x: 3.1942 mm | y: 1.0419 mm | WD | 9.6 mm | 20.00 kV | 200 x | BSED

500 µm

24520_FeCrNi

FeCrNi 450° C 2500h

Element	CrK	FeK	NIK
Area 1	16,1	70,8	13,1
	Wt%	70,4	12,4
	At%	94,6	0,1
Area 2	5,3	94,3	0,1
	Wt%	78,5	9,1
	At%	78,1	8,6
Area 3	12,4	93,3	0,4
	Wt%	92,9	0,4
	At%	94,8	0
Spot 1	6,3	94,5	0
	Wt%		
	At%		
Spot 2	5,2		
	Wt%		
	At%		

FeCrNi 450° C 5000h

In the area penetrated by the PbBi there is a depletion of Ni and Cr, even if the latter has areas of enrichment, probable decomposition of the FeCr alloy after Ni leaching or a carbide

FeCrNi 550° C
64h, 94h, 200h, 1000h, 2500h, 5000h

FeCrNi 550° C 64 h

Element	PbM	BiM	CrK	FeK	NiK
Spot 1	0.7	0.2	20.2	78.8	
Spot 2	0.2	0.1	21.5	78.2	
Spot 3			10.7	88.5	0.8
Spot 4			11.4	87.8	0.8
Spot 5			10.6	89.0	0.4
Spot 6	6.4		11.3	88.4	0.4
Spot 6 (bulk)	1.8		12.7	80.3	0.7
			14.1	83.4	0.7
			16.6	82.4	1.0
			17.6	81.4	1.0
			17.1	70.4	12.6
			18.2	69.9	11.9

TOTAL Cr Depletion

Cr Gradient

FeCrNi 550° C 200 h

Spot	Element	PbM	BIM	CrK	FeK	NIK
Spot 1	Wt%	1,4	0,6	12,3	84,5	1,3
	At%	0,4	0,2	13,2	85,0	1,2
Spot 2	Wt%			9,1	90,9	0,0
	At%			9,7	90,3	0,0
Spot 3	Wt%			12,5	87,0	0,5
	At%			13,3	86,2	0,5
Spot 4	Wt%			10,4	89,3	0,4
	At%			11,0	88,6	0,4
Spot 5	Wt%			20,8	64,6	14,6
	At%			22,2	64,0	13,8
Spot 6	Wt%	4,9	2,6	11,2	80,6	0,6
	At%	1,4	0,7	12,7	84,6	0,6
Spot 7	Wt%			17,4	69,6	13,0
	At%			18,6	69,2	12,3

FeCrNi 550° C 1000 h

FeCrNi 550° C_ PM 08620_2500 & 5000h

FeCrNi 550° C 5000 h

TOTAL Cr Depletion
Cr Gradient

PM 08720 FeCrNi 550° C, 2500h

Element	OK	PbM	BIM	CrK	FeK
Wt%	0,4	2,3	1,5	12,9	83,0
At%	1,4	0,6	0,4	13,9	83,6

(EDX area @ 500X Mag)

FeCr 450° C

23620 FeCr 450° C, 1000h – CS Polished side

Area	OK		CrK	FeK
	Wt%	At%		
Area 1	17,7	82,3	17,1	82,9
	18,8	81,2		
Area 2	18,1	81,9	17,1	82,8
	17,1	82,8		
Area 3	18,2	81,8	17	83
	17	83		
Area 4	18	82	17,2	82,8
	17,2	82,8		
Area 5	18,2	81,8	17	81,2
	17	81,2		
Area 6	17,3	76,9	1,8	16,5
	16,5	81,7		
Area 7	16,8	77,3	17	83
	17	83		
Area 8	18	82	18	82
	18	82		
punto 1	30	24,8	6,8	24,8
	6,8	24,8		
punto 2	48,5	11,4	3,4	11,4
	3,4	11,4		
	4,5	70	15,5	70
	15,5	70		
	13,9	71,3	14,8	71,3
	14,8	71,3		

Oxygen only
in the LBE

23920 FeCr 450° C, 2500h

Very thin oxide with thickness around 700nm

Element	Wt%	At%
OK	05.32	16.39
PbM	01.58	00.38
CrK	16.05	15.22
FeK	77.05	68.02

23920 FeCr 450° C, 2500h

Some spots with failure of the FeCr oxide and growth of the external magnetite.

24020 FeCr 450° C, 5000h

Element		OK	CrK	FeK
Area 1	Wt%	22,9	1,1	76,1
	At%	50,8	0,7	48,5
Area 2	Wt%	24,6	29,1	46,3
	At%	52,5	19,2	28,4
Area 3	Wt%		17,4	82,6
	At%		18,5	81,5
Area 4	Wt%		17,5	82,5
	At%		18,6	81,4

Same feature seen @2500h spots with failure of the FeCr oxide and growth of the external magnetite

24020 FeCr 450° C, 5000h

	Element	OK	PbM	CrK	FeK
Spot 1	Wt%	22,7	12,6	1,4	56,4
	At%	55,1	2,4	1	39,2
Spot 2	Wt%	23,6		34,1	42,3
	At%	51		22,7	26,3
Spot 3	Wt%	7,5		20,1	72,5
	At%	21,7		18	60,4
Spot 4	Wt%			17,4	82,6
	At%			18,5	81,6
Spot 5	Wt%			17,7	82,3
	At%			18,8	81,2

The spots with the double oxide layer have a chromium depletion in the interface area with the steel, followed by an innermost area that is enriched with chromium. Furthermore, at this point there is a further transition zone, below the chromium-enriched zone and the bulk. Feature probably due to the fact that the Cr below the FeCr oxide is trapped in the internal oxidation zone particles

FeCr 550° C

FeCr 550° C 1000h

- Typical scenario - infiltration LBE with a depth 7-10 μm
- Such zones are accompanied by a depletion in Cr
- No presence of O.
- The zone depleted in Cr extends well beyond the infiltration limit of LBE.
- Islands of Cr oxide are observed at the steel-LBE interface, usually submerged by LBE (the native oxide floating)

FeCr 2500h, 550° C

The line scan shows the Cr rich oxide layer and below the penetration zone of the Pb in the sample, which in this case reaches thicknesses of the order of 20-30 μm .

07920 FeCr 5000h, 550° C

penetration zone of the Pb in the sample, which in this case reaches thicknesses of the order of 40-50 μm .

Element	OK	PbL	BiL	CrK	FeK	
Spot 1	Wt%	30.8	28.6	10.6	27.5	2.5
	At%	71.7	5.1	1.9	19.7	1.7
Area1	Wt%				17.9	82.2
	At%				18.9	81.1
Area 2	Wt%	12.4	35.1	39.8	2.8	9.9
	At%	56.8	12.4	13.9	3.9	13.0

FeCrNi Summary

- At the two temperatures tested the dissolution attack started after a very short time of exposure
- The dissolution measured as depth of the zone penetrated by the LBE is faster increasing the temperature
- Both Ni and Cr are leached by the LBE, the Cr dissolution is slower and a decreasing trend in going toward the surface is observed in the Ni depleted zone
- The Corrosion rates of the model alloy result much higher compared with the data reported in the literature for the 316 SS
- It is generally observed a delay and a similar corrosion rate in the non-polished side of the samples (not shown here)
- No dissolution reported for the same material in the same experimental campaign by CVR in Pb

FeCr Summary

- ✓ @ 450°C very thin oxide slowly growing & no dissolution attack at any time
- ✓ Nevertheless, increasing the time of exposure and starting at 2500h locally there is a change in the oxidation mechanism and a dual layer oxide develops in spots spread all over the sample surface
- ✓ The magnetite spots have circular shape and looks like rosettes over the FeCr oxide that covers the sample
- ✓ Below the FeCr layer growing inward there is an internal oxidation zone
- ✓ Outside of the dual layer spots, the growth rate of the oxide in 18 Cr alloy is much slower than the rate of 9Cr F/M steels (F82H, EM10, P91) reported in the literature
- ✓ Increasing the temperature the oxide fails and start the dissolution attack
- ✓ The dissolution rate is much lower than that of the FeCrNi alloy 50 mm vs. 2500 mm at 5000h
- ✓ Also in this case it is observed a delay and a similar corrosion rate in the non-polished side of the samples (not reported here)
- ✓ No dissolution reported for the same material in the same experimental campaign by CVR in Pb

THE END
Questions?

1101 0110 1100
0101 0010 1101
0001 0110 1110
1101 0010 1101
1111 1010 0000

Titolo della presentazione - luogo - data (più pagina - vedi istruzioni per visualizzazione in tutta la presentazione)

Performance of austenitic steels 316L and 15-15Ti in lead coolant

Lukáš Košek

and Lucia Rozumová, Martina Pazderová, Anna Hojná, Claudia Aparicio

Contents

Materials	
Specimens	
Equipment	
Experimental conditions	
Evaluation	
316	
15-15Ti	
Open questions – oxygen, deformation	
Conclusion	

Materials:

316L

TIG plate

316L_30

Gas tungsten arc weld (TIG):
Outokumpu (30 mm thickness)
Arcelor Mittal (40 mm thickness)

SAW plate

316L_70

Submerged-arc welding (SAW)
75 mm 316L(N)-IG
by Walter Tosto

15-15Ti

1.4970 material was produced by CSM, (Roma, Italy)
heat treatment 1230°C/3 h, hot rolling to 20 mm, cold
rolling, annealing (1150 °C/5 min), quenching and final
cold working to 14 mm thick plate. Average grain size 19
µm

Materials: 316L

15-15Ti

Material	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	Co	N	Cu	Ti	Fe
15-15Ti	0.085	0.87	1.42	0.04	0.004	14.70	15.60	1.54	0.005	0.004	0.01	0.43	Bal.
EDX check*	-	0.7	1.4	-	-	14.6	15.2	1.4	-	-	-	0.3	63.7

Specimens

316L 30mm

15-15 Ti

Default GEMMA specimen:
Electric discharge machining from plate
Lathe turning
Degreasing

Material research Loop MATLOO

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Test conditions

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Target parameters:

Hot leg 480°C

Cold leg 400°C

Oxygen 1E-7 wt. %

Velocity 1.6 m/s

X1 316H, 15-15TI_3(2)

8228

X1 316H

1009

X1 316L_30
316L_70
1515TI

1010

X1 316_70_2,
1515TI_2

1895

X1 316L_3

1031

X1 316L_70_3

1992

X1 316L_70_2

4224

X1 321_2

865

X1 316L_4

316H5

X1 316L_70, 316L_70_blasted

4027

316L_70_3, 316L_blasted, el. polished EP + m. polished MP

X2 316L_30, 316L_70, 15-15TI#8, 15-15TI#14

8116

X2 316L_30, 316L_70, 15-15TI#1, 15-15TI#2

16175

15-15Ti

15-15Ti_1000

15-15Ti_1000_2

15-15Ti_2000

15-15Ti_2000_2

15-15Ti_4000

15-15Ti_4000_2

15-15Ti_8000

15-15Ti_8000_2

15-15Ti_8000_3 (2)

15-15Ti_16000

15-15Ti_16000_2

1000h

2000h

4000h

8000h

16000h

316L 30mm

316L_30_1000

316L_30_2000

316L_30_4000

316L_30_8000

316L_30_16000

316L 70mm

316L_70_1000

316L_70_2000

316L_70_4000

316L_70_8000

316L_70_16000

316L_70_1000_3

316L_70_2000_2

316L_70_4000_2

316L_70_8000_3

Generalized corrosion process

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1. Thin film formation

2. Thin film failure

3. Thin film regeneration

4. Surface depletion

316L 2000h

316L 4000h

15-15Ti 16000

316L 16000

15-15Ti 4000_2

316L 1000h

Thin film - thickness

A	Thin film
B	Depleted zone
	Base metal

	1 000 h	2 000 h	4 000 h	8 000 h	16 000 h
316L	A (nm)	40-100	30mm: 120-150; 70mm: 90-120, 150 peels off, 270nm new layer	140-160	30mm: 200-240; 70mm: 130nm
	B (nm)	NA	on specimen loosing thin film 0- 1000nm	30mm: 500-800; 70mm: 350-900	30mm: 1.4-1.6um; 70mm: 3.4-3.9um
15-15Ti	A (nm)	NA	80-150	200	1: 70-80nm; 2: 150-180nm
	B	NA	1.1-1.3um	1.5um	1: 2.5um; 2: 4um

Thin film - composition

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XRD with Co source:

316L 8000h

trevorite (NiFe_2O_4)

chromite (FeCr_2O_4)

magnetite (Fe_3O_4).

Near surface:

chromium oxide (Cr_2O_3)

chromium carbide (Cr_{23}C_6)

316L 16000h

15-15 Ti 16000h

SEM-EDS:

8000h: $\text{FeCrMn}_{2.5}\text{O}_5$

16000h: $\text{FeCr}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_2$

XRD with Co source:

15-15Ti 1000, 8000h

FeCr_2O_4

NiFe_2O_4

$\text{Cr}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{1.6}\text{NiO}_4$

$\text{Cr}_{1.4}\text{Fe}_{0.6}\text{NiO}_4$

MnCr_2O_4

MnFe_2O_4

Fe_3O_4 (inverse)

CrFeMnO_4

Other phases $\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{C}$, Mo_6Fe_7)

1000h doesn't contain

Cr_{23}C_6 , $\text{Cr}_{16}\text{Fe}_6\text{NiC}_6$

15-15 Ti 18 000h

nichromite (NiCr_2O_4)

manganochromite (MnCr_2O_4)

magnetite (Fe_3O_4).

Chromium carbide is present Cr_{23}C_6

also titanium carbide TiC

Thin film - TEM

¹⁶316L 30mm 16 000h

316L: BCC: 90% Fe
20% Cr 6% Cr
12% Ni 4% Ni
2% Mn
2% Mo

FCC: 66% Fe
9% Cr
23% Ni

Mo 33% Cr
12% Mn
10% Fe
45% O

15-15 Ti 16 000h

15-15Ti: BCC: 90% Fe
15% Cr 6% Cr
15% Ni 4% Ni
1.5% Mn
1.5% Mo

FCC: 64% Fe
10% Cr
25% Ni

Ti

15% Cr
18% Mn
8% Fe
61% O ¹²

Thin film - failures

316L 2000h

New film

As soon as 1000h, there is evidence of thin film loss on **some** specimens.

Opening opportunity for Pb penetration

Thin film - failures

Deep oxidation, on first 4000hr specimens with duplex scale formation. Outer oxide $\sim \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

316L_30mm
4000h (0-4 000h)
111

316L_70mm 4000h
(7-11 000h)
H2020-GEMMA Project No. 755269

Results

316L _N		exp. time (h)	measured loss (mm)	loss + average oxidation (mm)	loss + maximum oxidation (mm)
Specimen					
316L_30_1000h no.17		1010	0.001	0.001	0.005
316L_70_1000h		1010	0.000	0.000	0.002
316L_70_3_1000h		1031	-0.001	na	na
316L_30_2000h no.33		2187	0.003	0.005	0.008
316L_70_2000h		2187	0.003	0.004	0.006
316L_30_4000h no.18		4082	0.013	0.015	0.018
316L_70_4000h		4027	0.014	0.015	0.017
316L_30_8000 no.8		8116	0.004	0.004	0.010
316L_70_8000h		8116	0.004	0.004	0.004
316L_30_16000 no.14		16175	0.003	0.003	0.008
316L_70_16000h		16175	0.002	0.007	0.012

15-15Ti		exp. time (h)	measured loss (mm)	loss + average oxidation (mm)	loss + maximum oxidation (mm)
Specimen					
15-15Ti_1000		1010	0.002	0.003	0.003
15-15Ti_2000		2187	0.004	0.006	0.011
15-15Ti_4000		4082	0.005	0.007	0.010
15-15Ti_4000_2		4034	0.003		
15-15Ti_8000_2*		8116	0.00	0.00	0.01
15-15Ti_16000_2*		16175	0.00	0.01	0.01

original dia. +- 0.02um

2000h

typical

duplex

316L 30mm 2000 h trans.

316L 70mm 2000 h long.

316L 30mm 2000 h long.

316L 70 2000

Pb in BSE

316L 70mm 2000_2 h trans.

Very rare loc. oxidation - 2 sites

1515Ti 2000 h trans.

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Repeated spec.

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Electron Image 1

4000h

316L 30mm 4000 h trans.

316L 70mm 4000 h trans.

316L 70mm 4000 h long.

316L 30mm 4000 h trans.

1515Ti 4000 h trans.

1515Ti 4000 h long.

1515Ti 4000 h trans.

1515Ti 4000 h long.

SEM HV: 15.0 kV WD: 9.02 mm View field: 50.0 µm Det: BSE
LYRA3 TESCAN 10 µm

16 000h

316L 70mm 16 000 h trans.

316L 70mm 16 000 h long.

1515Ti 16 000 h trans.

1515Ti 16 000 h long.

70mm – rel. large areas

30mm – trans. (rare oxidation)

transverse

longitudinal

316L surface effects

Standard finish – lathe turned

316L_30_1000

316L_70_1000_3

316L_70_2000

316L_70_2000_2

316L_30_4000

316L_70_4000

316L_30_8000

316L_70_8000_3

EL polished

Mech. polished

Blasted

4000hr

Mechanical polishing

316L 4000hr

Electropolished

8000hr

Mech polish

El polish

Discussion

Corrosion was quite low, hard to measure.

With prolonged time, there is higher probability of localized oxidation outbreak.

The deformed surface – work hardened layer increase resistance of Pb penetration.

theoretical explanation is faster Cr, Mn diffusion (than lattice diffusion).

As depletion progress – there is less and longer pathways.

But 8000 specimens are practically intact and look better than (1)2-4 000h, regardless the material.

Possible reasons

no thermal cycling

uneven flow division between sections

lower oxygen concentration in late state

of experiment

(but 1000h specimen undergo exactly 1 cycle)

(flow meter was calibrated every replacement period)

(beginning at same time = same oxygen content)

Is the low oxygen the explanation? – slowing the oxidation to the level, where diffusion can supply the oxide regeneration without much defects from fast grow.

Localized oxidation – can start at Fe rich grain and progress inside when oxide fails.

Localized Pb penetration – may start at grain boundary or in Ni rich site when oxide fail.

Open question

Effect of oxygen?

316L_30_4000

316L_70_4000

FM vs Stainless steels

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316L

15-15Ti

Grade 91

Specimens exposed to flowing lead of 1.6m/s velocity, with oxygen content 1E-7wt.% O at 480°C for 8000hr

Stainless steel – the differences

316L

316H

AISI 15-15Ti

AISI 321

Specimens exposed to flowing lead of 1.6m/s velocity, with oxygen content 1E-7wt.% O at 480°C for 4000hr

Thanks for attention

GEneration iv Materials Maturity GEMMA project
<http://www.eera-jpnm.eu/gemma/>

GEMMA

Quantification - methodology

Diameter →

Image →

Surface LOM/SEM →

FIB →

Thin layer evaluation

Metallographic sections
Transversal / Longitudinal

24x 15° or 5x on each side
SEM image of 100µm view field

10 sites evaluated + the worst damage

Micro-VU Vertex 251HM

Fit whole diameter with circle with accuracy 2µm

Quantification example

15-15Ti 4000hr

Diameter estimation by fitting circle on cross-section after exp.:

Half of (as-received – fitted circle) = 8

The worst damage

Material loss = 8+7µm

Performance of 316L welds

Lukáš Košek

and Lucia Rozumová, Martina Pazderová, Anna Hojtná, Claudia Aparicio

Materials:

316L

Gas tungsten arc weld (TIG):
 Outokumpu (30 mm thickness)
 Arcelor Mittal (40 mm thickness)

Submerged-arc welding (SAW)
 75 mm 316L(N)-IG
 by Walter Tosto

Materials:

TIG

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GTAW weld is a Thermanit GE-316L. The ferrite content of the wire is 7%, which is within the requirements on 5-15%

TIG Weld deposit chemical composition

	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	Nb	N	Co	Cu
Min		0.30	1.00			18.00	12.00	2.5				
Max	0.030	0.60	2.50	0.025	0.020	20.00	14.00	3.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3
Heat	0.012	0.42	1.72	0.018	0.009	18.33	12.17	2.53	0.02	0.05	0.0	0.1

SAW

The wire-flux combination for the SAW weld is a Thermanit GE-316L and Avesta Flux 805. Ferrite content of weld deposit is 11%

H2020-GEMMA Project No. 755269

Material	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	Nb	N	Co	Al	Fe
316L SAW [wt. %] [1]	0.015	0.55	1.34	0.016	0.006	19.49	12.16	2.48	0.013	0.053	0.03	-	Bal.
EDS check [wt. %]	-	0.5	1.5	-	-	20.2	12.2	2.2	-	-	-	-	63.4
	-	-	1.5	-	0.57	20.7	10.5	1.9	-	-	-	0.37	64.4

Specimens

316L TIG

316L SAW

- Default GEMMA specimen:
- Electric discharge machining from plate
- Lathe turning
- Degreasing

Test conditions

Target parameters:

Hot leg 480°C

Cold leg 400°C

Oxygen 1E-7 wt. %

Velocity 1.6 m/s

X1	TIG	1895	SAW_2	TIG_2
X1	SAW_2	1177	TIG_2	
X1	SAW_2	4034	SAW_2	
X1	TIG_2	3863	TIG_2	
X1	TIG_SAW	2187	X1	TIG_2_SAW_2
X1	TIG_SAW	4082		
X2	TIG_SAW	8116	X1	TIG_3_SAW_3
X2	TIG_TIG_2_SAW	16175		

SAW

SAW_1000

SAW_1000_2

SAW_2000

SAW_2000_2

SAW_4000

SAW_4000_2

SAW_8000

SAW_8000_2

TIG_16000

TIG_18000

TIG

TIG_1000

TIG_1000_2

TIG_2000

TIG_2000_2

TIG_4000

TIG_4000_2

TIG_4000_3

TIG_8000

TIG_8000_2

TIG_16000

TIG_16000_2

1000h

2000h

4000h

8000h

16000h

316L

Specimen	exp. time (h)	measured loss (mm)	loss + average oxidation (mm)	loss + maximum oxidation (mm)
316L_30_1000h no.17	1010	0.001	0.001	0.005
316L_70_1000h	1010	0.000	0.000	0.002
316L_70_3_1000h	1031	-0.001	na	na
316L_30_2000h no.33	2187	0.003	0.005	0.008
316L_70_2000h	2187	0.003	0.004	0.006
316L_30_4000h no.18	4082	0.013	0.015	0.018
316L_70_4000h	4027	0.014	0.015	0.017
316L_30_8000 no.8	8116	0.004	0.004	0.010
316L_70_8000h	8116	0.004	0.004	0.004
316L_30_16000 no.14	16175	0.003	0.003	0.008
316L_70_16000h	16175	0.002	0.007	0.012

SAW

Specimen	exp. time (h)	measured loss (mm)	loss + average oxidation (mm)	loss + maximum oxidation (mm)
SAW_1000	1010	0.004	0.004	0.004
SAW_1000_1	1177	0.004	na	na
SAW_2000	2187	0.003	na	na
SAW_2000_2	1895	0.009	0.009	0.010
SAW_4000	4082	0.004	0.005	0.008
SAW_8000_2	8228	0.005	0.005	0.008
SAW_16000	16175	0.002	0.003	0.009

TIG

Specimen	exp. time (h)	measured loss (mm)	loss + average oxidation (mm)	loss + maximum oxidation (mm)
TIG_1000	1010	0.002	0.003	0.003
TIG_1000_2	1177	0.003	na	na
TIG_2000	2187	0.004	0.004	0.005
TIG_2000_2	1895	0.000	na	na
TIG_4000	4082	0.003	0.004	0.006
TIG_8000_2	8228	0.009	0.009	0.011
TIG_16000	16175	0.001	0.001	0.005
TIG_16000_2*	16175	0.00	na	na

Thin film - composition

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XRD with Co source:

316L 8000h

trevorite (NiFe_2O_4)

chromite (FeCr_2O_4)

magnetite (Fe_3O_4).

Near surface:

chromium oxide (Cr_2O_3)

chromium carbide (Cr_{23}C_6)

**TIG 8000 and SAW
same as base material:**

trevorite (NiFe_2O_4)

chromite (FeCr_2O_4)

magnetite (Fe_3O_4).

Chromium oxide Cr_2O_3

1000h

SAW 1000h

TIG 1000h

SEM HV: 15.0 kV	WD: 9.02 mm	LYRA3 TESCAN
View field: 25.0 µm	Det: BSE	Performance in nanospace
SEM MAG: 13.8 kx	Date(m/d/y): 06/24/20	

SEM HV: 15.0 kV	WD: 9.07 mm	LYRA3 TESCAN
View field: 50.0 µm	Det: BSE	Performance in nanospace
SEM MAG: 6.92 kx	Date(m/d/y): 06/22/20	

316L 30mm 2000 h trans.

316L 30mm 2000 h long.

316L 70mm 2000 h long.

316L 70mm 2000_2 h trans.

SAW 4000_2

TIG 4000

Pb penetration

316L 30mm 4000 h trans.

316L 70mm 4000 h trans.

316L 70mm 4000 h long.

Pb penetration wasn't evaluated

SAW 4000_2

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SAW 4000_3

H2020-GEMMA Project No. 755269

Al-Si-O particles

8000h

SAW 8000

TIG 8000

SAW 8000_2

TIG_8000_2

Majority of the surface was penetrated by Pb to ~1µm

TIG 800_2

SAW 8000

O-Mn-Al-Si particle

SAW 16 000

TIG 16 000

Rare, deep oxidation

TIG 16000

TIG 16000_2
typical

316L 70mm 16 000 h trans.

841

316L 70mm 16 000 h long.

Thanks for attention

GEneration iv Materials Maturity GEMMA project
<http://www.eera-jpnm.eu/gemma/>

GEMMA

Performance of austenitic steels 316L with Al_2O_3 and FeCrAl coatings in lead coolant

Lukáš Košek
and Zuzana Žofková, Lucia Rozumová, Martina Pazderová, Anna Hojná

As-received specimens

Al₂O₃ coating

Before exposure

Material	Al	O
EDX check Al ₂ O ₃	40.3	59.7
	40.6	59.4
	37.2	62.8
	39.2	60.8
	37.3	62.7

FeCrAl coating

Before exposure

Material	Si	Mn	Cr	Ni	Mo	Al	Fe
EDX check FeCrAl	0.4	0.6	14.4	8.0	1.0	14.2	61.3
	-	0.7	10.8	17.3	-	22.8	48.5
	0.8	0.8	19.6	3.3	1.4	7.0	67.1
	1.5	1.2	21.7	4.6	1.4	4.0	65.5

H2020-GEMMA Project No. 755269

Material	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	Co	N	Cu	Ti	Al	O	Fe
316L	0.026	0.4	1.71	0.017	0.0013	17.22	12.27	2.46	0.025	0.073	0.12	0.01			Bal.
EDX check*		0.9	1.2			18.6	11.6	1.0							66.3

Substrate

Test conditions

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Target parameters:

Hot leg 480°C

Cold leg 400°C

Oxygen 1E-7 wt. %

Velocity 1.6 m/s

FeCrAl

FeCrAl_1000_2

FeCrAl_2000_2

FeCrAl_4000_2

FeCrAl_8000_2

FeCrAl_16000

FeCrAl_1000

FeCrAl_2000

FeCrAl_4000

FeCrAl_8000

Al₂O₃

Al₂O₃_1000_2

Al₂O₃_2000_2

Al₂O₃_4000_2

Al₂O₃_8000_2

Al₂O₃_16000

Al₂O₃_1000

Al₂O₃_2000

Al₂O₃_4000

Al₂O₃_8000

1000h

53

2000h

4000h

8000h

16000h

Al₂O₃

1000h

54

Al₂O₃_1000

Al₂O₃_2000

Al₂O₃_4000

Al₂O₃_8000

Al₂O₃_16000

Al₂O₃_1000_2

Al₂O₃_2000_2

Al₂O₃_8000_2

FeCrAl

FeCrAl_1000

FeCrAl_2000

FeCrAl_4000

FeCrAl_8000

FeCrAl_16000

FeCrAl_1000_2

FeCrAl_2000_2

FeCrAl_4000_2

FeCrAl_8000_2

Performance in flowing Pb

1000 h

Al_2O_3

1000 h

FeCrAl

detail of oxidation

Performance in flowing Pb

156

Al_2O_3

2000 h

$FeCrAl$

2000 h

Performance in flowing Pb

157

Al_2O_3

4000 h

FeCrAl

4000 h

Performance in flowing Pb

158

Al_2O_3

8000 h

detail of oxidation, longitudinal cross-section

longitudinal cross-section: corrosion damage of the substrate

FeCrAl

8000 h

H2020-GEMMA Project No. 755269

EDX line scan across coating/substrate interface

Performance in flowing Pb

Al_2O_3 16000 h

transverse cross-section: Pb penetration

longitudinal cross-section: corrosion

EDX revealed a Cr depleted, recrystallized zone beneath the surface oxide in bulk of steel with minimum Cr concentration at interface between oxide and metal. In the middle of depleted zone the Ni concentration is increased above original steel concentration.

Distribution of oxide layer size around the perimeters of transverse (left) and longitudinal cross-sections (right)

160

Al₂O₃

1000 h

4000 h

2000 h

8000 h

16000 h

Performance in flowing Pb

FeCrAl 16000 h

(1) coating – top layer, Cr/Al 14 at.%

(2) coating – Ni and Al rich layer

(3) coating – Cr rich layer

(4) coating – Cr rich layer

substrate

Top layer of the coating was based on Fe/Cr/Al/Ni (60/14/14/8). Ni and Al rich layer was found below the top layer. The rest of the coating contained higher amount of Cr (approx. 20 at%), Al content decreased towards the substrate and Ni content was minimized. Surface of steel was not depleted by Cr and Ni and no Pb penetration into the coating was found.

Specimen name	As-received diameter [mm] **	After exposure diameter [mm] ***	Change [µm]
FeCrAl 1000	9.953	9.962	9
FeCrAl 1000_2	9.956		
FeCrAl 2000	9.954	9.961	7
FeCrAl 2000_2	9.961		
FeCrAl 4 000	9.960		
FeCrAl 4000_2	9.957	9.963	6
FeCrAl 8000	9.955		
FeCrAl 8000_2	9.957	9.961	4
FeCrAl 16 000	9.952		
** Kinex 7031-02-025			
*** Mitutoyo C/N 293-100-10			

Conclusion

Long term exposure of Al_2O_3 coating (average thickness of 41 μm) and FeCrAl (average thickness of 42 μm) and deposited on 316L substrate was performed.

No visible changes can be found at Al_2O_3 coating's surface after the exposure and the elemental composition of the coating did not change.

Pb penetration into the Al_2O_3 coating was not caused by dissolution of the coating but the presence of cracks allowed access of Pb to the coating.

Even short exposure was enough for growth of very thin oxide film on coating/substrate interface. Thin oxide film was non-continuous.

After long term exposure EDX revealed a Cr depleted, recrystallized zone beneath the surface oxide in bulk of steel with minimum Cr concentration at interface between oxide and metal. In the middle of depleted zone the Ni concentration is increased above original steel concentration.

FeCrAl coating was compact and dense with no imperfections. Cross-section analysis revealed changes in coating's composition but it was found that even 16 000 h of exposure did not affected the corrosion resistance, no damage was found and elemental composition remained stable.

Thanks for attention

GEneration iv Materials Maturity GEMMA project
<http://www.eera-jpnm.eu/gemma/>

Corrosion behaviour of TIG welded 15-15 Ti steel and different coatings in Pb

A. Heinzl, A. Weisenburger

Detonation gun (DG)

- Al_2O_3 / amorphous Al_2O_3 composite coating
- only on one side
- ~3 μm thick
- mirror like surface

- Al_2O_3 covered all over
- ~ 30-34 μm thick
- rough surface
- high number of closed pores inside

Pack cementation

- Typical diffusion layer
- covered all over
- ~48 μm thick
- Consists of a smaller outer layer with a higher amount of Al and Ni and a much thicker inner layer, in which the Al amount gradually decreases towards the bulk (Al diffusion layer)

	480°C			550°C		
	2000h	6500h	10000	5000	10000	10000
316L / Pulsed Laser Deposition	X	X	X	X	X	X
316L / Detonation-Gun	X	X	X	X	X	X
316L / Pack cementation	X				X	

550°C / 5000h

All sample were cleaned with ethanol-acetic acid-H₂O₂

Wt%	Bright area	Dark area
O	33.29	35.64
Al	51.39	54.78
Pb	15.32	9.58

The surface investigations show a change in the structure at the immersed part. A grain growth can be observed with pores in between. The change is not detectable by XRD.

Both samples show severe exfoliation of the coating and an oxidation of the bulk. At 10000h it seems that cracks occur, where oxygen can react with the bulk surface. The formed Fe oxide growth outwards. **Dissolution attack!**

170

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171

No detachment or change of the coating is visible over time.

The cracks and holes have no negative effects on the corrosion.

2000h

6500h

10000h

2000h

6523h

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	Ø thickness [µm]	Ø thickness [µm]
Oxide layer	16.9	43.5
magnetite	6.6	19.7
Spinel with roots	10.2	23.8

The oxide layer consists of Fe-O (magnetite), followed by a Fe-Cr spinel and Fe-Cr spinel roots.

The oxide layer is growing over time.

The slightly brighter parts in the Fe-oxide are Pb inclusions

After 10000h: in areas where the magnetite layer has flaked off, Pb can penetrate up to 25 µm (30% of the surface from the cross section)

bulk

Heat affected zone
(HAZ)

grain coarsening of up to
50 μ m

HAZ and weld

grains are elongated and
oriented in the direction
of the heat flow

The exposure times were 5000h and 10000h

- Magnetite, Fe-Cr spinel and Fe-Cr spinel roots are formed at the surface, but in all zones Pb can penetrate into the spinel and forms locally Pb enriched areas.
- Depth of the HAZ spinel roots is larger than that in the bulk and the weld.
- In the weld region the Ti precipitations are smaller than in the bulk and enriched at the grain boundaries, but an influence on the oxide formation due to these precipitations is not detectable

The oxide layer are growing over time, the thickest oxide layer are on the HAZ (44% more than on the bulk material)

On the welding area great parts of the magnetite layer spalled off, but the spinel or rests of the spinel layer are still there.

with 10^{-7} wt% oxygen.

exfoliation of the coating, an oxidation of the bulk and solution attack by Pb occurred.

	480°C			550°C		
	2000	6500	10000	5000	10000	
PLD	+	+	+	-	-	
DG	+	+	+	+	+	
Pack cementation	+	+	+			

Results of corrosion tests in static Pb of Base Materials and Welds

H2020 GEMMA Workshop on HLM corrosion, 3 November 2021

S. Bassini, A. Fiore, C. Ciantelli, C. Sartorio, S. Cataldo, M. Angiolini

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0001 0110 1110
1101 0010 1101
1111 1010 0000

Test Matrix in static Pb, 480°C, low Co

Static Pb corrosion of GEMMA 316L (annealed) and 15-15Ti AIM-1 (cold-worked) and their welds SAW and TIG at 480 °C, low Co < 10⁻⁷ % wt., up to 10000 h (5000 h for 316L materials)

Material	Totale Time (h)	Time at C _o < 10 ⁻⁷ (h)	T average (°C)	C _o average < 10 ⁻⁷ (% wt.)
316L BM	1028	1007	481 ± 2	6.5E-10
	2013	2003	480 ± 1	1.6E-09
	5010	4997	481 ± 2	1.7E-10
316L + SAW weld	1005	997	480 ± 1	2.8E-10
	2010	2001	480 ± 1	2.5E-10
	5014	4914	480 ± 1	6.1E-09
316L + TIG weld	1002	972	480 ± 1	6.5E-09
	2008	1994	479 ± 1	1.5E-08
	5037	5016	480 ± 1	3.1E-10

Material	Totale Time (h)	Time at C _o < 10 ⁻⁷ (h)	T average (°C)	C _o average < 10 ⁻⁷ (% wt.)
15-15Ti BM	1029	1018	481 ± 2	2.6E-09
	5059	5034	481 ± 2	8.6E-10
	10006	9992	479 ± 1	1.5E-10
15-15Ti + TIG weld	1029	1018	481 ± 2	2.6E-09
	5059	5034	481 ± 2	8.6E-10
	10003	9973	479 ± 2	2.7E-10

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Sample preparation

- Chemical composition available in “Weld specimen specifications and characterizations”, D2.1.
- 316L BM and 15-15Ti BM samples were prepared flat 40x8x3 mm with polished surface finishing.
- 316L BM samples were obtained by TIG plate 30 mm, by cutting far away from the weld zone.
- 316L TIG and SAW weld samples were prepared by cutting the weld transversally. The samples were polished on both sides
- 15-15Ti TIG samples were prepared by cutting the weld transversally. The samples were polished on one side (the other side remained «as-fused»)

Exposure in static Pb, 480°C, low Co

Set-up RACHEL lab (Brasimone)

- Large capsules for long-term exposure
- T max operation = 550 °C
- HLM inventory (Pb 99.99%) = 5.5 Kg
- Up to 6 samples for capsule
- For deoxygenation, injection of Ar-H₂ gas with H₂ 10-15 % vol.
- Pre-calibrated [O] sensors (Pt/LSM-air ref.)

[O] sensors (700mm)

Example of operative conditions

	Pb	Ag	As	Bi	Cu
% wt.	99.9965	0.0001	0.0002	0.0010	0.0006
	Sb	Sn	Zn	Cd	Ni
	0.0003	0.0002	0.0002	< 0.0001	< 0.0001

Low oxygen $10^{-10} - 10^{-9}$ % wt.
 Pb Temperature $480 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$
 Pb 99.99 % purity

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Methodology - Analysis

The samples were cutted, embedded in resin, grinded and polished for SEM-EDX analysis.

- Portions of 316L BM (and 15-15Ti BM) were placed in «sandwich» position for SEM investigation surface.
- Average and maximum corrosion values evaluated in the «affected zones»
- TIG and SAW weld samples were cutted almost in the middle of the fused zone (FZ), identified by etching with oxalic acid solution and then observing/checking x and y coordinates on SEM.
- Average and maximum corrosion values evaluated in the «corroded zones» of the weld (FZ).
- Evaluation was also tentatively performed in the HAZ regions, considered within 3 mm near the FZ.

316L BM – General view

- Solution corrosion front with Ni leaching and Pb penetration increasing with the exposure time (Max penetration: 28 µm 1000h, 41 µm 2000h, 89 µm 5000h)
- After 1000h some portions were still unaffected, but for the other exposure times corrosion effects are spread above the whole surface.

316L BM – Composition

EDX maps 2000h

Thin oxidation (< 1µm), not identified in composition
 Ni depletion – missing or very low (2-3 % wt.) and Pb penetration
 Cr segregation – rich islands (40 % wt.) and poor islands (14 % wt.)

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EDX point 5000h

Porosity

Element	OK	PbM	CrK	FeK	NIK
Spot 1	0.0	1.5	14.1	78.4	1.7
Spot 2	0.0	0.4	15.3	79.0	1.6
Spot 3	0.6	1.0	39.9	50.4	3.6
	1.9	0.3	41.7	49.1	3.3
Spot 3	0.5	0.4	39.2	51.8	3.1
	1.7	0.1	41.0	50.4	2.9

316L SAW weld (FZ) – General view

- Unaffected surface after 1000h. Solution corrosion front with Ni leaching and Pb penetration for 2000 and 5000h
- (Max penetration: 30 µm 2000h, 56 µm 5000h)
- Lower corrosion compared to 316L BM

316L SAW weld (FZ) - Composition

δ-ferrite (unaffected weld)

different color contrast

EDX point 5000h

Element	OK	SiK	MoL	PbM	CrK	MnK	FeK	NiK
Spot 1	Wt% 0.9	0.7	2.9	0.9	40.8	0.5	52.0	1.4
	At% 3.0	1.3	1.6	0.2	42.1	0.5	50.0	1.3
Spot 2	Wt% 0.9	0.9	2.0	2.0	20.6	0.4	72.7	1.5
	At% 1.8	1.8	1.2	0.5	22.1	0.4	72.6	1.4
Spot 3	Wt% 0.8	0.8	2.9	0.5	17.1	0.5	76.5	1.7
	At% 1.6	1.6	1.7	0.1	18.3	0.5	76.2	1.6
Spot 4	Wt% 0.9	0.9	3.2	0.5	41.2	0.4	51.1	2.8
	At% 1.7	1.7	1.8	0.1	43.3	0.4	50.1	2.6
Spot 6	Wt% 0.9	0.9	2.6	1.2	14.8	0.3	78.4	1.8
	At% 1.7	1.7	1.5	0.3	16.0	0.3	78.5	1.7
Spot 5 (bulk)	Wt% 0.8	0.8	3.0	0.9	18.2	1.4	63.6	12.1
	At% 1.7	1.7	1.8	0.3	19.6	1.4	63.8	11.5

Ni depletion – missing or very low (2-3 % wt.)
 Pb penetration and porosity in the dissolution layer
 Cr segregation – rich islands (41 % wt.) and poor islands (15 % wt.) particularly visible at the longest exposure time (5000h)

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316L TIG weld (FZ) – General view

- Unaffected surface after 1000h. Presence of a thin oxidation layer.
- Solution with Ni leaching and Pb penetration for 2000 and 5000h
- (Max penetration: 18 μm 2000h, 38 μm 5000h)
- Lower corrosion compared to 316L BM

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Comparison between 316L materials (BM and FZ)

Maximum and average corrosion and Pb penetration are larger for 316L BM than for TIG and SAW weld FZ

- Unaffected surface after 1000h for TIG and SAW.
- Delayed corrosion for FZ compared to BM
- After 5000h, max penetration higher for SAW compared to TIG, but average values are similar.

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15-15Ti BM – General view

- Solution corrosion front with Ni leaching and Pb penetration increasing with the exposure time (Max penetration: 6 µm 1000h, 55 µm 5000h, 112 µm 5000h)
- After 1000h some portions were still unaffected, but for the other exposure times corrosion effects are spread above the whole surface.

15-15Ti BM – Composition & detachments

EDX maps 5000h

Ni depletion – missing or very low (2 % wt.) – and Pb penetration
 Cr segregation – rich islands (34 % wt.) visible at high exposure time
 (5000h and 1000h)

Presence of cracks and
 detached portions of the porous
 FeCr layer in 10000h samples
 (brittleness)

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15-15Ti + TIG weld (FZ) – General view

- After 1000-5000h portions of surface were still unaffected, but for the 10000h corrosion is spread above the whole FZ (about 6 mm in length).
- Solution front with Ni leaching and Pb penetration increasing with the exposure time (Max penetration: 19 µm 1000h, 26 µm 5000h, 67 µm 5000h)

15-15Ti + TIG weld (FZ) - Composition

EDX point 10000h

Element	OK	PbM	TiK	CrK	FeK	NiK
	Wt%	At%	Wt%	At%	Wt%	At%
Area 1	3.9	8.2	0.3	16.1	68.9	2.7
Area 2	13.0	2.1	0.3	16.5	65.7	2.4
Area 2 (bulk)	3.8	2.1	0.4	14.8	63.4	15.5
	12.2	0.5	0.5	14.7	58.5	13.6
Punto 1	3.3	1.8	0.1	10.7	82.1	1.9
	10.7	0.5	0.1	10.7	76.3	1.6
Punto 2	7.2	13.9	0.2	49.0	27.7	1.8
	22.7	3.4	0.3	47.3	24.9	1.6

Ni depletion – missing or very low (2-3 % wt.)

Pb penetration and porosity

Cr segregation – rich islands (49 % wt.) particularly visible at the longest exposure time (10000h). Not so much visible at 5000h.

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Comparison between 15-15Ti materials

Maximum and average corrosion and Pb penetration are globally larger for 15-15Ti BM than for TIG weld FZ

- At 1000h, max and average penetration higher for TIG compared to BM, but the trends change after 5000h (higher corrosion for BM)

Summary of BASE MAT corrosion

- 1) Exposure in static Pb 480°C and low oxygen shows about solution corrosion for 316L and 15-15Ti AIM-1 BM, with Ni selective leaching and formation of a porous Fe-Cr ferrite layer.
- 2) Cr segregates creating Cr-rich and Cr-poor islands in the ferrite corrosion layer (look at miscibility gap and low Cr solubility in Pb).
- 3) After the shortest exposure time 1000h, portions of the samples were still unchanged but 316L material is more affected than 15-15Ti. For the other exposure times (2000, 5000, 10000h) the corrosion affected the whole surfaces.
- 4) Larger corrosion observed for 316L material compared to 15-15Ti (given the same exposure time, 1000 and 5000h).
- 5) After the longest exposure (10000h), the FeCr ferrite layer was detached in some portions of the samples of 15-15Ti BM.

Comparison of BASE MAT corrosion

Summary of WELD (FZ) corrosion

- 1) Exposure in static Pb 480°C and low oxygen shows about solution corrosion for welds in the FZ (but also in HAZ), with Ni selective leaching and formation of a porous Fe-Cr ferrite layer.
- 2) After the shortest exposure time (1000h and 2000h), some portions of the samples were still unchanged but for the other exposure times (5000, 10000h) the corrosion affected the whole surfaces.
- 3) Cr segregates creating Cr-rich and Cr-poor islands in the ferrite layer.
- 4) Lower corrosion observed for weld materials (FZ) compared to relative BMs. Investigation of the reason is ongoing, focusing on the possible effect of δ -ferrite presence and distribution (expected to be different between TIG/SAW).

Comparison WELD and BM corrosion

HAZ behaviour in 316L materials

Corrosion evaluation in the HAZ was performed in the first 3 mm near the FZ, but the large grain dispersion makes hardly possible a numerical comparison related to grain size. For the comparison with the FZ, various features should be considered such as the density of the heat flux, the amount of δ -ferrite, composition of the filler, variation of the grain....

HAZ behaviour in 15-15Ti materials

Corrosion evaluation in the HAZ was performed, but large grain dispersion makes hardly possible a numerical comparison related to grain size. If compared to BM and FZ region, HAZ shows larger corrosion in terms of average value and comparable corrosion to BM in terms of maximum value. This could be related to an effect of the grain shape (fine in weld, strained in BM and enlarged in HAZ).

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H2020 GEMMA Workshop on HLM corrosion, 3 November 2021

Preliminary results in dynamic Pb of materials and coatings in BID1

H2020 GEMMA project Task 4.1

Workshop on HLM corrosion

3 November 2021

C.Ciantelli, S. Bassini, A. Fiore, C. Sartorio, S. Cataldo, M. Angiolini

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Exposure in dynamic Pb 550°C - BID1 pool

Isothermal small pool (Pb = 150 L) for testing OCS, used for exposure in dynamic conditions for GEMMA.
 The system has been equipped with a cold finger @ 420° C to simulate a cold point

T_{max} : 550°C (316Ti)

Mixer for dynamic HLM conditions

1 oxygen sensor 700 mm

gas system with H₂/O₂

Pb flow evaluation - BID1 pool

CFD calculation for Pb flow

Chaotic Pb flow and transversal circulation along vessel walls of 0.12 m/s at the mixer velocity (69 rpm)

Test section and oxygen condition- BID1 pool

O₂ concentration = 10⁻⁸%wt

Materials and Geometry

Material	Shape
Alumina coating by D-Gun on 15-15Ti	Cylinder (dia: 9 mm, L_{eff} : 30 mm)
Alumina coating by PLD on 15-15Ti	Cylinder (dia: 9 mm, L_{eff} : 30 mm)
Al-based diffusion coating by industrial Pack Cementation on AISI 316L	Cylinder (dia: 9 mm, L_{eff} : 30 mm)
AFA 6	Flat (33 x 8 x 2 mm)
AFA 9	Flat (33 x 8 x 2 mm)

- For cross-section analysis the samples were cutted, embedded in resin, grinded and polished for SEM-EDX analysis.
- For planar analysis, fragment of alumina coated specimens underwent a cleaning process and coated with gold (15 nm thick) to enhance the electrical conductivity of the surface.

Test Matrix of materials and coatings exposed in BLD1

Material	Exposure time (h)	Shape
15-15Ti + D-Gun	No (virgin)	cylinder
15-15Ti + D-Gun	2200	cylinder
15-15Ti + D-Gun	4100	cylinder
15-15Ti + D-Gun	8000	cylinder
15-15Ti + D-Gun	4100	cylinder
15-15Ti + PLD 1µm	8000	cylinder
15-15Ti + PLD 1µm	No (virgin)	cylinder
15-15Ti + PLD 5µm	4100	cylinder
15-15Ti + PLD 5µm	8000	cylinder
15-15Ti + PLD 5µm	No (virgin)	cylinder
316L + Pack Cem	2200	cylinder
316L + Pack Cem	4100	cylinder
316L + Pack Cem	8000	cylinder
316L + Pack Cem	No (virgin)	flat
AFA 6	4100	flat
AFA 6	8000	flat
AFA 6	No (virgin)	flat
AFA 9	4100	flat
AFA 9	8000	flat
AFA 9	No (virgin)	flat

- Exposure tests were planned up to 8000h
- Extraction of samples was performed at 2200, 4100h

15-15Ti+ DGun_2200h

Planar analysis

Element	OK	AlK	CrK	FeK	PbM
Wt%	39.3	50.6	0.3	2.0	7.8
Area	55.7	42.5	0.1	0.8	0.9

Presence of Pb in some spots

- Penetration of Pb in coating defect
- Penetration of Pb stops in the middle of the coating
- Thickness comparable to the value of virgin one
- No presence of corrosion and/or degradation on substrate

15-15Ti+ DGun_4100h

Planar analysis

- Coating surface with roughness but compact and continuous
- Thickness comparable to the value of virgin one
- Cross-section analysis reveals localized oxidation on substrate under alumina coating: Ni depletion, Cr or FeCr oxide formation, no penetration of Pb
- Thickness of altered area is around 6 μm

Element	OK	AlK	SiK	MoL	TiK	CrK	MnK	FeK	NiK
Spot 1	28.8	11.9	1.3		2.1	44.1	4.1	7.6	
At%	53.1	13.0	1.4		1.3	25.0	2.2	4.0	
Spot 2	23.2	6.2	4.5			38.0	3.1	25.1	
At%	47.2	7.4	5.2			23.7	1.8	14.6	
Spot 3		0.4	1.6	0.6	8.5		71.5	17.5	
At%		0.8	0.9	0.7	9.1		71.8	16.7	
Spot 4		0.9	1.7	0.4	14.8		1.5	65.2	15.5
At%		1.8	1.0	0.5	15.8		1.5	64.8	14.7

15-15Ti+PLD 1µm_4100h

- Smooth, compact and continuous surface
- Homogeneous distribution of the elements
- Alumina coating is adherent to 1515Ti substrate
- No corrosion/dissolution appear on 1515Ti alloy
- No Pb penetration occurs on alumina coating and on 1515Ti alloy

15-15Ti+PLD 5µm 4100h

Planar analysis

Element	OK	AlK	SiK	MoL	CrK	FeK	NiK
Area 1 Wt%	51.0	49.0					
Area 1 At%	63.7	36.3					
Area 2 Wt%	1.1	4.5	0.8	1.8	13.0	63.2	14.3
Area 2 At%	3.6	8.6	1.5	1.0	13.0	58.6	12.6
Area 3 Wt%			1.0	1.8	15.1	65.0	15.4
Area 3 At%			2.0	1.1	16.2	64.6	14.5

- Smooth, compact and continuous surface
- Homogenous distribution of the elements
- Alumina coating is adherent to 1515Ti substrate, thickness of around 5 µm
- No corrosion/dissolution appear on 1515Ti alloy
- No Pb penetration occurs on alumina coating and on 1515Ti alloy

AISI 316L+Pack cementation – 2200h

Planar analysis

Element	OK	NIK	AIK	SiK	MoL	CrK	FeK
Wt%	17.4	6.8	24.3	0.8	1.4	8.5	40.9
At%	35.8	3.8	29.6	0.9	0.5	5.4	24

HV mag det x 1.1393 mm WD 30 µm
15.00 kV 3.845 x ETD y 1.2171 mm 10.4 mm 39519 Pack cem corrosio

Virgin

Element	OK	NIK	AIK	CrK	FeK
Wt%	7.1	11.0	18.4	9.5	54.0
At%	18.1	7.6	27.7	7.4	39.3

HV mag det x 1.1393 mm WD 10 µm
15.00 kV 7.868 x ETD y 1.2171 mm 10.4 mm 39519 Pack cem corrosio

External zone 9 µm
Diffusion layer 51 µm
Al, O
Al, Ni
Al, N

HV mag det x 0.8147 mm WD 40 µm
15.00 kV 3.000 x BSED y 8.2013 mm 10.1 mm 39519 Pack cem corrosio

- Planar analysis shows superficial oxidation, with a light increase of Al content
- Thickness of diffusion layer and external zone comparable to virgin
- Presence of precipitates NiAl, AlN, Al₂O₃ (already observed in virgin)
- No Pb penetration in diffusion layer
- Light increase of O is detected near the interface

Element	OK	AIK	Mol	CrK	PbM	FeK	NIK
Wt%	3.1	0.1	2.9	17.3	0.3	63.7	12.6
At%	10.1	0.2	1.6	17.3	0.1	59.5	11.2
Area	3.1	7.6	2.8	16.9	0.2	59.3	10.2
Area	9.4	13.6	1.4	15.8	0.1	51.4	8.4
Area	3.3	15	2.9	11.1	0	54.8	1.3
Area	9.4	25.1	1.4	9.6	0	44.5	10

HV mag det x 3.4332 mm WD 50 µm
15.00 kV 2.003 x BSED y 5.8579 mm 10.1 mm 39519 Pack cem corrosio

AISI 316L+Pack cementation – 4100h, Planar Analysis

AlK

CrK

NiK

Area	OK	AlK	CrK	FeK	NiK
Wt%	8.1	24.7	19.3	39.5	8.3
At%	19.1	34.7	14.0	26.8	5.4

OK

FeK

- Similar morphology compared to virgin specimen
- Increase of Al and Cr is detected on surface

AISI 316L+Pack cementation – 4100h, Cross Section Analysis

- Thickness of diffusion layer and external zone comparable to virgin
- No evidence of corrosion
- Presence of precipitates NiAl, AlN, Al₂O₃ (as already observed in virgin)
- No Pb penetration in diffusion layer
- Slight change of Al and Cr content within the external zone
- Light increase of O is detected near the interface

AFA 6_ 4100h

- No evidence of severe dissolution, but a slight enrichment of Cr is observed near the surface, within the external zone
- Presence of precipitates with high Nb content (as already observed in virgin)
- No Pb penetration in steel
- Light increase of O is detected near the interface

AFA 9_4100h

- No evidence of severe dissolution, but a slight enrichment of Cr is observed near the surface, within the external zone
- Presence of precipitates with high Nb content (as already observed in virgin)
- No Pb penetration in steel
- Light increase of O is detected near the interface

Thank you

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1101 0110 1100
0101 0010 1101
0001 0110 1110
1101 0010 1101
1111 1010 0000

Results from corrosion tests performed in the framework of GEMMA

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316L IN STATIC LEAD AT 550 °C

Expansion of the GEMMA round robin on 316L-DEM(ETRA) by two other materials, i.e. 316L-NET and 316L-SAW

- Fine-turned and polished surface, respectively.
- Nominally 10^{-7} and 10^{-9} %, respectively, of oxygen dissolved in liquid lead.
- 1000 h

	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	Cu	V	W	Co
DEM	16.73	9.97	2.05	1.81	0.67	0.23	0.07	0.02	N/A
NET	17.33	12.22	2.43	1.79	0.45	0.20	N/A	N/A	0.170
SAW	17.22	12.27	2.46	1.71	0.40	0.12	N/A	N/A	0.025
	Al	Ti	Ta	Nb	P	N	C	S	B
DEM	0.018	0.0058	N/A	0.000	0.032	0.029	0.019	0.035	N/A
NET	0.035	0.0076	<0.0010	0.0046	0.027	0.067	0.022	0.001	0.0007
SAW	N/A	0.01	0.003	0.00	0.017	0.073	0.026	0.0010	0.0007

Composition (% by mass) of 316L materials tested.

... and 316L-SAW.

Microstructure in the solution-annealed state of 316L-DEM ...

... 316L-NET ...

316L IN LEAD: EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

- Approximately 9 kg lead, contained in corundum crucible.
- Two sample holders with each three samples of dimensions $\text{Ø}8 \times 10$ mm.
- Sample holder made of nickel-lean iron-chromium steel.
- Steel surface exposed to the liquid metal of overall 4350 mm^2 , of which 2430 mm^2 fall on the austenitic samples.
- Two oxygen sensors positioned 47 and 96 mm below the lead surface, respectively.
- Automated control of dissolved oxygen with the aid of gas/liquid oxygen transfer.
- Gas introduced above the lead surface.
- Sensor residing closer to the surface serves as the reference for oxygen control.

Sample holders, with samples still attached, after exposure to lead at nominally 10^{-9} % dissolved oxygen.

316L IN LEAD: SPECIFICATION OF EXPOSURE CONDITIONS

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Nominally 550 °C/10⁻⁷ % oxygen

- “Fresh” lead.
- 546–552 °C.
- 0.9×10⁻⁷–2.3×10⁻⁷ % oxygen.
- Oxygen content near the bottom of the lead pool increases (?).
- Exposure time 1008 h.

Nominally 550 °C/10⁻⁹ % oxygen

- “Used” lead.
- 546–553 °C.
- Oxygen decreasing from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻⁹ % during first 45 h.
- Mostly 0.9×10⁻⁹–60×10⁻⁹ % oxygen.
- Oxygen content relatively high near ...

... the bottom of the pool (?).

– Exposure time 1008 h.

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316L IN LEAD: QUANTIFICATION OF STEEL DEGRADATION

Before the test

- Initial diameter in the centre of the samples determined with the aid of a laser-micrometer.

Identifier	Surface finish	D_0 (μm)	Uncertainty (μm)
DEM01	Fine-turning	8000	± 2
DEM02	Polishing	7986	± 1
DEM03	Fine-turning	8000	± 2
DEM04	Polishing	7990	± 2
NET01	Fine-turning	8003	± 3
NET02	Polishing	7997	± 2
NET03	Fine-turning	7999	± 2
NET04	Polishing	7964	± 3
SAW01	Fine-turning	7998	± 3
SAW02	Polishing	7938	± 4
SAW03	Fine-turning	7972	+4/-10
SAW04	Polishing	7957	± 3

After the test, in the light-optical microscope

- Remeasurement of steel diameter (D_{ST}) and calculation of steel recession ΔX_{ST} by comparison with D_0 .
- Measurement of corrosion scale thickness ΔX_{CS} .
- 12 and 24 measurements of unaffected steel diameter and scale thickness, respectively, by turning the sample by each 15° between the measurements.

316L IN LEAD: RESULTS FROM LIGHT-OPTICAL MICROSCOPY

Surface of 316L-DEM, fine-turned, 10^{-7} % oxygen.

Cross-section of 316L-DEM, polished, 10^{-7} % oxygen.

- Features of original surface conserved in the surface of corrosion scales.
- Corrosion scale typical for selective leaching of nickel and chromium, manganese.
- Near-surface fringe (appearing dark) counted in the thickness of the scale (depletion zone).
- Large particles in solidified lead only at nominally 10^{-7} % dissolved oxygen, and only where “dark fringe” is present.

- Observed scale thickness corresponds well with the recession of sound steel.

- Corrosion depth after 1000 h of order 150–200 μm , slightly higher at nominally 10^{-9} than at 10^{-7} % oxygen.

- Protective scale (thin oxide) on about 50 % of the evaluated circumference exceptionally observed for two of the samples; same position in the testing device.

Cross-section of 316L-SAW, polished, 10^{-9} % oxygen.

316L IN LEAD: RESULTS FROM SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

Cross-section of 316L-SAW, fine-turned, 10^{-9} % oxygen.

Cross-section of 316L-NET, polished, 10^{-7} % oxygen.

– Example of protected surface.

- Large particles in solidified lead observed in the test at nominally 10^{-7} % oxygen are sulphide (chromium, manganese).
- “Dark fringe” (light-optical microscope) is depleted in iron; low ferrite content.
- Sulphide in the ferrite-depleted part and main body of the corrosion scale.

316L IN LEAD: SULPHIDE FORMATION

316L-DEM, fine-turned,
10⁻⁷ % oxygen.

(a) Sulfide

316L-SAW, fine-turned,
10⁻⁹ % oxygen.

Original position
of the steel surface

(c) Ferrite/sulfide mixed spectrum

Nominally 550 °C/10⁻⁷ % oxygen

- Near-surface disintegration of the depletion zone (ferrite) once formed in the course of selective leaching of nickel, chromium, manganese.
- Large sulphide particles result from chromium or manganese residues in the dissolving ferrite and sulphur available in “fresh” lead (<4×10⁻⁶ % by mass).

Nominally 550 °C/10⁻⁹ % oxygen

- Manganese-rich sulphide forms in the ferrite-poor portion of the depletion zone at the lower sulphur concentration in “used” lead.

316L IN LEAD: CONCLUSIONS

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For 550 °C, 9 kg static lead, gas/liquid oxygen transfer across the lead surface

- Selective leaching of nickel, chromium, manganese is the dominant degradation mechanism at dissolved oxygen in the order of 10^{-9} to 10^{-7} % by mass.
- Depth of corrosion is about 150–200 μm after 1000 h.
- Peculiar oxygen distribution in the testing device, possibly contributing to effect of position in the device on delay in the initiation of selective leaching.
- Sulphide rather than oxide formation with corresponding threshold concentration of $<4 \times 10^{-6}$ % sulphur.
- Insignificant effect of the particular heat of 316L.

Clear chromium enrichment along with incomplete nickel depletion of particular grain in 316L-SAW, fine-turned, 10^{-7} % oxygen.

EXPERIMENTS IN THE CORRIDA LOOP

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CORRIDA loop

- 1000 kg LBE circulating in the loop.
- Ø8x35 mm samples in two vertical test sections.
- Gas/liquid oxygen transfer controlled with the aid of electrochemical sensors.

Nominal conditions of the test

- LBE.
- 500 °C (~325 °C cold leg temperature).
- 10⁻⁶ % dissolved oxygen.
- 2 m/s flow velocity of LBE (5.3 kg/s).

CORRIDA: TESTED STEELS

	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	Cu	V	W
T91-DEM	8.99	.11	.89	.38	.22	.06	.21	.01
T91-OTH	8.76	.099	.862	.597	.317	.054	.186	N/A
316L-DEM	16.73	9.97	2.05	1.81	.67	.23	.07	.02
316L-OTH	16.71	11.22	3.02	1.69	.30	N/A	N/A	N/A
1.4970	15.95	15.40	1.20	1.49	.52	.026	.036	< .005
	Co	Al	Ti	Nb	P	N	C	S
T91-DEM	N/A	.0146	.00348	.06	.021	.0442	.1025	.0004
T91-OTH	.019	.021	.003	.073	.019	N/A	.088	.0006
316L-DEM	N/A	.018	.0058	.000	.032	.029	.019	.035
316L-OTH	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1.4970	< .01	.023	.444	< .0005	< .01	.0090	.101	.0036

Steel composition in % by mass.

Tempered martensite in T91-DEM (left) and T91-OTH (bottom).

Austenitic microstructure in (from left to right) solution-annealed 316L-DEM and 316L-OTH, and cold-worked 1.4970.

CORRIDA: SPECIFICATION OF EXPOSURE CONDITIONS

Exposure times 504, 1007 and 2016 h.

Temperature 500 (± 5) °C.

Oxygen concentration 10^{-6} %, with temporary excursion to $> 10^{-5}$ % during the test for 1007 h (mobilisation of oxide deposited in the loop).

Flow velocity 2 (- 0.2) m/s, gradually decreasing to 1.6 m/s during the test for 2016 h.

CORRIDA: RESULTS FOR T91 AT 500 °C/10⁻⁶ % OXYGEN

Friable internal oxidation zone and partial loss during preparation especially for fine-grained T91-DEM.

Intermediate as to observations at 550 °C (no magnetite, internal oxidation) and 450 °C (magnetite, insignificant internal oxidation).

Signs of steel solution found after shortest exposure time.

Scale formation starts with internal oxidation, after failure of thin, once protective surface film.

CORRIDA: QUANTIFICATION OF OXIDATION OF T91

For short exposure times, metal recession more reliably estimated from inward growing part of the oxide scale than from change in sample diameter.

Activation energy of oxidation

in LBE, 10⁻⁶ % oxygen, 2 m/s, based on parabolic rate law

$$\Delta x^2 = k_2 t + C_2$$

assumed for associated metal recession.

	$k_2 \times 10^2$ ($\mu\text{m}^2/\text{h}$)	C_2 (μm^2)
450 °C	1.53	11.8
500 °C	5.05	30.7
550 °C	8.08	536
Apparent activation energy:		83 kJ/mol

CORRIDA: RESULTS FOR 316L AT 500 °C/10⁻⁶ % OXYGEN

316L-DEM

- Only protective oxide scale, typically chromium- or silicon-rich.

316L-OTH

- After 2016 h, 20 % of investigated surface shows solution-based corrosion, with up to 12 µm corrosion depth.
- Almost complete loss of nickel, loss of half of the chromium in originating depletion zone.
- Higher nickel (and molybdenum) content as well as less silicon and manganese or (slightly) larger grain size in comparison to 316L-DEM.

CORRIDA: RESULTS FOR 1.4970 AT 500 °C/10⁻⁶ % OXYGEN

10–20 % of investigated surface affected by solution-based corrosion (1007, 2016 h), with order of 10 µm corrosion depth.

Singular event of accelerated oxidation alternative to solution — higher chromium content, cold-worked material, in contrast to 316L.

Rugged steel surface indicates solution-based corrosion with depletion zone detached — observed already after 504 h.

CORRIDA: CONCLUSIONS FROM TESTS IN FLOWING LBE AT 500 °C, 10⁻⁶ % DISSOLVED OXYGEN, ~2 m/s FLOW VELOCITY

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Oxidation of ferritic/martensitic T91

- As for layers occurring in the oxide scale, oxidation at 500 °C is intermediate between 450 and 550 °C.
- Porous magnetite that tends to buckle and detach, friable internal oxidation zone.
- Activation energy (450–550 °C): 83 kJ/mol, same order but somewhat lower than found at 10⁻⁷ % dissolved oxygen.

Austenitic 316L, 1.4970

- Incubation time of solution-based corrosion (selective leaching) comparable to 550 °C but clearly shorter than at 450 °C and otherwise comparable conditions.
- After failure of initially formed protective oxide, higher tendency of 1.4970 to oxidise in accelerated fashion, alternatively to element dissolution.

Results from corrosion tests performed in the framework of GEMMA

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Design requirements of CRAFT

- Corrosion test loop for MYRRHA candidate materials;
- Representative (or conservative) temperature, oxygen and flow:
 - Cold leg down to 200°C (mechanical design temperature 450°C);
 - Hot leg up to 550°C;
 - Flow rate up to 5 m/s in the material test section;
 - LBE Flow rate measurement;
 - Reliable oxygen measurement;
 - Automated oxygen control;
 - Replacement of material samples under protective atmosphere;
 - Automated process regimes and safety responses.

Design implications

- Mechanical design of hot (<560°C) and cold leg (<450°C);
- Material choice: hot leg: P22; cold leg: 316L;
- 2" piping with insert in test section to locally increase flow;
- Coriolis flow meter coupled with MHD pump;
- 12 oxygen sensors (9 in hot leg, 3 in cold leg);
- Electronic mass flow controllers for oxygen regulation;
- Glovebox with controlled Ar atmosphere over test section;
- PLC control of process and safety.

CRAFT construction

From design to mechanical complete in 7 months

Commissioning tests (1)

- 23 bar pressure test with demin water
 - Loop drained and dried by heating and purging dry nitrogen
 - Cold (23°C) and hot (250°C) vacuuming of the loop (to $5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar)
- Dry run of aircooler and MHD pump
- Hot (250°C) purging with Ar and vacuuming of the loop
- Filling test with LBE from atmospheric condition at 250°C
 - Some gas pockets in undesired locations.
- Filling test with LBE from vacuum at 250°C
 - Replacement of pressure regulators on test section vessels.
- Build up of ΔT of 250-350°C
- Test and optimize PID control aircooler
- Test automatic dump sequence.

Commissioning tests (2)

- Test automated filling sequence
- Tightness issue with actuated valves due to solidification of LBE on the stem of the valve
- Split tracing/heating control and add thermocouples
- Automated filling, build up ΔT of 250-400°C (flow: 8 kg/s)
- Decrease of oxygen concentration

start testing oxygen control in pulse mode

- Setpoint 1: 250mV: ok ± 5 mV
- Setpoint 2: 270 mV: ok, in 8 min
- Setpoint 3: 240 mV: O₂ insufficient (20 ml/min)

Exposure cycles

Cycle	Maximum exposure duration, hours	T HL-CL	Target [O], mass %	Materials	Start	End
1	2.100	450-270	7-4-3-2-1*10 ⁻⁷	T91, 316L, 1.4970	09/2013	12/2013
2	4.405	500-250	7.7*10 ⁻⁷	T91, 316L, 1.4970	03/2014	09/2014
3	19.732 9.728 for cladding tubes	400-220/270	1-2*10 ⁻⁷	T91, 316L, 1.4970, 1.4970 cladding tubes	07/2015	03/2019
4	4.102	400-270	< 10 ⁻⁹	1.4970 cladding tubes	04/2019	09/2019
5	4.320	400-220	2*10 ⁻⁷	1.4970 cladding tubes/ 316L/ 316L welds	11/2019	05/2020
6	> 16.000 (4.800 up to now)	400-220	2.5*10 ⁻⁷	1.4970 cladding tubes/ 316L/ 316L welds	12/2020	10/2023

Exposure cycles

Oxygen concentration control

- Oxygen measurements in 4 positions (before and after the test sections, in the conditioning tank, cold leg)
- 3 sensors in each position
- Conditioning tank purged with gas mixture – mass exchange on free surface of LBE
- Addition of oxygen to the gas mixture regulated to maintain the target oxygen concentration before the test sections
- Issues:
 - Difficult “to recover” after low oxygen test

Oxygen concentration

test sections
After

Major failures

- Tracer heaters failure of the draining line (2015)
- Local overheating of the draining lines
- Heaters replaced and control thermocouple changed
- Leakage in the economizer (2020)
- Crack of welded joint P22
- Cracked section replaced & weld heat treatment applied
- Flow meter failure(2021)
- Sensors malfunction
- Flow meter replaced

Major issues

- Pump motor vibrations
- Fixed with shock absorbers and sound insulation
- Pump motor sensitivity to electromagnetic waves
- Faradaic cage around the building
- Freezing of pressure gage tubes
- Wrong readings -> filter clogging overlooked
- Additional insulation, bypass around filter
- Pump power oscillations
- At high power levels
- Samples disconnected from the rig in cycle 3
- Probably due to test without spacers
- Pump power quick raise
- Adjustment of the spacers in the test sections

Research Centre

Temperature control

- Main heaters before the conditioning tank
- Heaters before each test section for fine tuning
- Automatic regulation of the cold leg minimum temperature
- PLC control of the air-LBE heat exchanger
- Tracers

- Commissioned 07/2013
- The first corrosion tests 10/09/2013 – 06/12/2013
- 12/2013-03/2014 modifications of CRAFT
 - Vacuum pump attached to the conditioning tank
- The second corrosion test 07/03/2014 – 29/09/2014
- Start of cycle 3
- 2015 - Failure of heaters in draining lines
- Cycle 3
- 2020 – Economizer leak
- 2021 – Flow meter failure - replaced

Corrosion Loop MATloo Operational experience

Lukáš Košek
and Lucia Rozumová, Martina Pazderová, Anna Hojná, Claudia Aparicio

Material research Loop MATLoo

Material research Loop MATLoo

Long term operation

OL_2

OL_1

OL_3

Regulation OI_03

Regulation OI_02

Oxygen control

Oxygen sensor YSZ with Bi/Bi₂O₃ reference

Gas based

Nominal operation: Ar 6.0 stream + Ar+10% O₂

Reduction phase: Ar-6% H₂

New loop

Oxygen consumption exponentially decreased during first hours of operation

After some time of operation, it required 0.015 – 0.004Nml/min

Hot leg: $\sim 2.2\text{m}^2$
Cold leg: $\sim 2\text{m}^2$

All oxygen is absorbed by Pb in Mass Exchanger
Measured by Orbisphere 410 instrument (with limit 0.5Pa)

Inlet: 5-7Pa O₂ @1bar
Outlet gas: 0.8Pa @ 2.08bar overpressure

Oxygen control by O₂ addition was possible due to loop oxidation, that decreases over time.

Pressure drop and oxygen

Spec. replacement

Corrosion products

Filter after ~20 000hr of loop operation
480/400°C

10um filter SS element

End 350°C to increase the deposits

Drained at low oxygen

Opened to air when Pb still liquid

Pb near surface was "sticky to SS"

Deposit analyses

Remaining Pb on top of filter

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Large XX - 90% Fe, low oxygen

EDS Layered Image 1

Al based coating

Cr based exfoliated oxide film

TOP side of
raw mesh

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Pb

steel cage
raw mesh
10um mesh
raw mesh

BOTTOM side
of raw mesh

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TOP side of fine mesh

BOTTOM side of fine mesh

Fe-O:
0.5-0.9
But also
70-86% Fe

Fe-O:
0.5-1.1
Cr < 0-2at. %

BOTTOM side of fine mesh

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Filtered Pb ~98%

Ni particles

EDS: 2-3% Ni + 10% O

Conclusion

Oxygen concentration at presence of corrosion products has significant impact on loop operation:

Pressure drop increase until content is reduced

Wetting of tools by coolant saturated by corrosion products

K27 submarine core meltdown

Effect of corrosion products on solid state Oxygen probe must be explored.

Mysteries:

Are oxidized corrosion products subject of mass transfer?

Where is Ni, the most soluble element in lead?

Thanks for attention

GEneration iv Materials Maturity GEMMA project
<http://www.eera-jpnm.eu/gemma/>

PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE GAINED FROM OPERATING THE LEAD-BISMUTH LOOP CORRIDA

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Background

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- Renewed interest in liquid lead and lead-bismuth eutectic (LBE) as coolants for nuclear reactors.
- Lead-cooled fast reactor is one of the concepts selected for the fourth generation of nuclear power plants.
- LBE is a candidate coolant and spallation-neutron source for the transmutation of long-lived isotopes in an accelerator driven sub-critical system (ADS).

Solution and re-precipitation of solid metal determined by the temperature-dependent solubility S_{Me} .

Benefit of partitioning and transmutation of nuclear waste as to final storage of the residues.

- Particular challenges identified in the very early studies:
 - Compatibility with steels.
 - In non-isothermal system, plugging of cold sections in consequence of material corrosion in the hot part.
 - Gain from oxygen addition to lead or LBE?

About the CORRIDA loop

- ❑ Important technical characteristics:
 - ❑ LBE inventory of 2500 kg.
 - ❑ 1000 kg LBE circulate in the loop, driven by electromagnetic pump.
 - ❑ Mass flow typically 5.3 kg/ s.
 - ❑ Up to 550 °C in the hot sections at a minimum temperature of ~300–385 °C in the cold leg.
 - ❑ Tubing and main components made of Steel 1.4571 (~316Ti).
 - ❑ Gas/ liquid oxygen transfer.
 - ❑ Oxygen transfer in the hot leg but on the way back to the cold section.

❑ Main aim:

- ❑ Long-term corrosion tests on steels in flowing lead-bismuth eutectic at 2 m/ s flow velocity, temperature between 400 and 550 °C, and 10^{-7} to 10^{-6} % dissolved oxygen.

Oxygen sensor used for oxygen control.

❑ “By-products”:

- ❑ Performance of the loop itself during long-term operation.
- ❑ Fundamental aspects of gas/ liquid oxygen transfer.
- ❑ Long-term performance of electrochemical oxygen sensors.

Details of oxygen transfer

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- ❑ Gas/ liquid oxygen transfer
- ❑ Across a plane LBE surface ($\sim 0.3 \text{ m}^2$).
- ❑ Gas introduced above the liquid-metal surface.
- ❑ Quasi-static gas, slow-flowing liquid metal (0.025 m/s at 5.3 kg/s).
- ❑ Commercial λ -probe monitoring the oxygen partial pressure in the gas plenum.
- ❑ Gas supply
 - ❑ Up to 500 sccm argon.
 - ❑ Up to 500 sccm argon–hydrogen ($5\% \text{ H}_2$) for regular operation, 2000 sccm for pre-conditioning.
 - ❑ Up to 10 sccm/ min air.
 - ❑ Humidifying the gas was abandoned with the automation of air addition.

Oxygen transfer device of the CORRIDA loop.

Before and after implementation of automated air addition.

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Electrochemical oxygen sensors

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- Pt/ air or Bi/ Bi₂O₃ reference electrode, with preference of Pt/ air.
- Electrolyte: γ -zirconia partially stabilized with yttria.
- Long electrolyte tube housed in a perforated steel sheath.
- Accuracy of ± 5 mV or better in tests against the Pb/ PbO equilibrium at 350–650 °C (Pt/ air).
- Four sensors in selected positions along the CORRIDA loop.

Design of oxygen sensors installed to the CORRIDA loop.

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Operating time of sensors in the loop

Accumulated operating time of oxygen sensors in the CORRIDA loop

Operating history of the CORRIDA loop

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Commissioning in Feb 2003.

Start of operation at 550 °C/ 10⁻⁶ % oxygen in Jul 2003.

Oxygen transfer with Ar-H₂-H₂O.

Manual air addition to Ar-H₂-H₂O. 😊

Optimization.

Dry gas.

Optimized manual air addition to humidified Ar. 😊

Tube failure at the inlet of the second test-section after total operation for 29,000 h. 😞

Return to 550 °C/ 10⁻⁶ % oxygen.

Automated air addition to Ar or Ar-H₂. 😊

Decreasing mass flow and mobile oxide deposits. 😞

Automation of hydrogen addition.

550 °C/ 10⁻⁷ % oxygen.

Tube failure at the bottom end of the first test-section after total operation for 66,000 h. 😞

450 °C/ 10⁻⁷ % oxygen.

Tube failure close to the weldment of the once replaced inlet piece after total operation for 47,500 (76,500) h. 😞

400 °C/ 10⁻⁷ % oxygen.

500 °C/ 10⁻⁶ % oxygen.

Problems with mass flow return. 😞

Total operation for 100,000 h in Feb 2016. 😊

Effective operation for 75,000 h in May 2017. 😊

Plug in the cold leg after total operation for 113,000 h (Dec 2017): 😞

Loop cannot be refilled after LBE dump.

Probing of the tubing of the loop

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- ❑ Tube failures in the hot leg
- ❑ Typical corrosion damage after operation of the tube for 66,000 h (F2).
- ❑ Detrimental effect of local flow patterns suspected for F1 (29,000 h) and F3 (47,500 h).

- ❑ Exposed to flowing LBE mostly at 550 °C, additionally at 450 °C and 10⁻⁷ % oxygen (T6–T9) as well as 400 °C/ 10⁻⁷% (T10).
- ❑ Samples from the cold leg mostly experienced 385 °C and 10⁻⁶ % oxygen or higher (T5), additionally 350 °C and 10⁻⁷ % oxygen (T11–T16).
- ❑ Pre-oxidized surface and periods of low oxygen concentration in the beginning of the exposure except for T3, T8 and T9.
- ❑ Tests on Steel 1.4571 under constant conditions available from the dedicated corrosion studies performed in the loop.

❑ Tube samples

- ❑ All in all 9 from the hot leg (T1–T4, T6–T10) after operation of the tubes for 6000 (T3) to 108,000 h (T10).
- ❑ Probing of the cold leg after 40,000 (T5) and 113,000 h (T11–T16).
- ❑ Nominal flow velocity of 2 (T7), 1.7 (T1–T4, T6, T8, T9) or 1 m/s (T5, T10–T16).

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Corrosion in the hot leg

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Sample T4 (left) and T10 (right) taken after operation for 40,000 and 108,000 h, respectively.

Phenomena and associated degradation strongly depend on position.

- Ranging from beneficial oxide scale formation to solution-based corrosion.
- Preferential nickel (chromium) transfer to the LBE in cases of solution.

Remarkable local nickel release in Test-section 1 correlates in time with partial plugging of the loop!

Mass flow during stage of partial plugging.

Precipitates or deposits in the cold leg

The plug that prohibited refilling the loop after last LBE dump?

Gas found after operation for 113,000 h and attempts to refill the loop

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Nickel chemistry in the loop

- Simplified thermochemical calculations
 - Pure solid phases.
 - Ideal diluted solution, no interaction of solutes.
 - Experimental solubility S_{Ni} in the nickel and NiBi domain.
 - Precipitation start temperatures as a function of dissolved nickel concentration in LBE at 10^{-6} and 10^{-7} % dissolved oxygen.

- Estimations for Grade 316 austenitic steel
 - Maximum nickel enrichment in LBE order of 10 % of nickel solubility.
 - At 10^{-6} % oxygen, re-precipitation of nickel most likely in the form of NiO.
 - At 10^{-7} % oxygen, NiO only at temperatures below the minimum along the loop ($\sim 300-385$ °C), otherwise NiBi.
 - NiBi₃ hardly possible during regular operation of CORRIDA, except for cold spots.

Observed plugging events

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- Partial plugging having started after 49,000 h of total operation
 - Accumulation of NiO in consequence of long-term operation at 10^{-6} % oxygen.
 - Eventual oxygen release inside the loop corroborates presence oxide.
 - Purging with argon–hydrogen gas improved the situation along with dumping the LBE and re-filling the loop.

NiBi₃ collected from sensor port.

Mass flow and dissolved oxygen during final stage of partial plugging.

- NiBi₃ plug in the cold leg after 113,000 h, in connection with dumping of the LBE
 - Calculations suggest NiBi₃ formation only in cold spots such as the ports of oxygen sensors.
 - Hypothesis: NiBi₃ formation in LBE residues inside CORRIDA after draining or during attempts to refill the loop.
 - 0.01 % nickel in the total LBE inventory of the loop allows NiBi₃ to precipitate at ~230 °C or less.

Interference of dissolved steel elements ...

- ... with oxygen control
- Oxidation of nickel in the cold leg.
- Dissolved oxygen concentration after transfer rises in order to compensate for the consumption.
- This concentration is limited by NiO formation at the temperature of oxygen transfer.
- Eventually, NiO formation in the cold leg determines the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the hot leg.

Specific to the CORRIDA loop!

Indicated concentration of dissolved oxygen for experiments at nominally 500 °C/ 10⁻⁶ % oxygen.

- ... with oxygen measurement
- Especially the sensor in the cold leg occasionally indicates by orders of magnitude lower oxygen concentration.
- Equilibration of mobile iron particles with dissolved oxygen, in dependence of local temperature?

- Re-precipitated iron or elements forming more stable oxides than iron collect at the sensitive element and oxidize?

Estimation of the long-term reliability of oxygen sensors

- ❑ Acceptance test before installation to the loop
 - ❑ Qualitative tests in the past.
 - ❑ Quantitative tests in the future.
 - ❑ Repeated test after some time of operation hardly possible
 - ❑ Difficult if not impossible to adjust an appropriate metal/ metal oxide equilibrium in the loop.
 - ❑ High risk that sensor breaks when being removed from the loop.
- ❑ Criterion for proper long-term operation in the CORRIDA loop
 - ❑ Compare the concentration of oxygen calculated from the four sensor signals.
 - ❑ Take into account oxygen consumption, accuracy of converting indicated voltage into oxygen concentration or temporary effects of sensor fouling.

Comparison of sensor output during steady operation at 400 °C/ 10⁻⁷ % dissolved oxygen.

Conclusions

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- ❑ LBE loops primarily made of austenitic steel:
- ❑ Corrosion phenomena on the tubing in the hot leg range from beneficial oxidation to solution-based corrosion.
- ❑ Plugging is dominated by dissolved nickel.
- ❑ The deposited nickel compound changes between 10^{-7} and 10^{-6} % oxygen, from NiBi to NiO.
- ❑ Nickel accumulation in the LBE inventory is to be considered in loop operation, especially for dumping and refilling.

- ❑ Oxygen transfer to flowing LBE:
- ❑ In the long run, both oxygen consumption and release in the loop have to be compensated for.
- ❑ Noticeable interference of dissolved nickel possible, especially in the case of the CORRIDA loop.
- ❑ Gas/ liquid transfer generally meets the variable request for oxygen addition or removal.
- ❑ Electrochemical oxygen sensors:
- ❑ Sensors with Pt/ air reference electrode operate reliably in the loop for >90,000 h at temperatures between ~400 and 550 °C.
- ❑ Temporary effect on oxygen measurement in the cold leg attributable to precipitated iron (or other elements forming more stable oxides than iron).

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Thank you for your attention!